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Draft Report:

**Resilience of Democratic Systems in Relation to the Misuse of AI, ICT,
and Other Emerging Technologies**

San Marino, 8 December 2025

Disclaimer: This document is prepared by the researchers of the Parliamentary Assembly of the Mediterranean (PAM), in their personal capacity. The opinions expressed in the report are the authors' own and may not reflect the views and positions of PAM.

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Executive Summary and Research Findings

This report represents the first step of a broader research project by the Parliamentary Assembly of the Mediterranean (PAM), focusing on threats to the resilience of democratic systems and processes, in face of external manipulation and interference, in particular resulting from the misuse of Artificial Intelligence (AI), ICT, and other emerging technologies. As a platform for dialogue among national Parliaments of the Euro-Mediterranean and the Gulf regions, this research is political-strategic, and its working methodology is based on facts. The report analyses the risks posed to the resilience of democratic systems by the speed and radical nature with which interference, disinformation and cyber-attack phenomena develop in the age of technological revolution. Technologies also represent the solution to the challenges and problems described here.

According to the report ‘How to Strengthen Democratic Resilience: Five Lessons for Democratic Renewal’ by the European Democracy Hub (December 2024), democratic resilience refers to the ability of a political system to withstand and adapt to challenges, threats, and crises without compromising its core principles, institutions, or processes. This concept involves maintaining the integrity of democratic governance, including the protection of civil liberties, the rule of law, free and fair elections, and political pluralism, even in the face of internal or external pressures. There is also a growing recognition that resilience includes the ability of political systems to modify their structures and processes to make them more robust – and more truly democratic. The approach taken in the report “How to Strengthen Democratic Resilience: Five Lessons for Democratic Renewal” highlights three strategic points: First, it recognizes that democracy is never consolidated and that the processes of protecting and building it are never-ending but require constant attention and investment. Second, it focuses on the weaknesses of states that are currently recognized as democratic as well as those that are clearly authoritarian. Third, it puts a greater emphasis on factors that can be shaped by civil society groups and international donors in the short term because of the imperative of identifying practical steps to halt the slide towards authoritarianism.¹

The following sections examine how to build the resilience of institutional systems. Liberal democracies are running substantial risks in this very delicate historical phase. Endogenous and exogenous causes contribute to the erosion of democratic values and systems, which are often ‘accused’ of failing to meet the basic costumes of the populations. When addressing the issue of democratic resilience, it is crucial to clarify the concept of the information ecosystem: this is the dynamic context in which human beings develop and use tools to process information that can be

¹ Cheeseman, N., Desrosiers, M.-E., Cianetti, L., & Gehrke, M. (December 2024). How to strengthen democratic resilience: Five lessons for democratic renewal. European Democracy Hub. https://europeandemocracyhub.epd.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/How-to-Strengthen-Democratic-Resilience-Five-Lessons-for-Democratic-Renewal_final.pdf

shared as a means of communication between them. Information ecosystems are communities linked by shared ideas and connected through technologies, from alphabets to artificial intelligence, which enable them to produce and share content.

In democratic systems, disinformation comes from within, not just from external actors: just think of what happened in England at the time of the Brexit referendum².

Another factor to highlight among the endogenous causes of the crisis of democracies is the growing spread of post-truth politics, which essentially denies factual truth in order to focus on emotion. The 2016 Word of the Year Oxford English Dictionaries wrote: Post-truth is the public burial of 'objective facts' by an avalanche of media 'appeals to emotion and personal belief.'³

Furthermore, the issue of 'strategic narratives' is very important, as these are not merely rhetorical tools: such narratives are fundamental to the projection of power and geopolitical success. In a world where information flows instantly and global competition is intensifying, the ability to develop and sustain a coherent narrative is as important as military or economic strength. Europe, in particular, is at a crossroads: if it succeeds in defining its own strategic narrative, the Old Continent will be able to position itself as a stabilizing force in a fragmented world.

Malevolent actors (state and non-state) exploit these difficulties of democracies in an organized and strategic way. Threats co-evolve in different ways, from narratives to disruption of physical and digital infrastructure, both in terms of disinformation and cyber-attacks: the strategies are very adaptive, able to act - in different contexts - on social cohesion and on widespread beliefs, and to attempt to impose, by malevolent actors, world views that would be alternative to democratic ones, emphasizing the limitations of the latter. In this complex landscape, this document analyzes strategies of online interference, disinformation and cyber-attacks, deployed by state actors most frequently identified in security and policy analyzes, as identified by the main global think tanks, and the US and UK security agencies: Russian Federation, People's Republic of China, Islamic Republic of Iran, North Korea. The findings of this report are summarized in the following table, distinguishing (not separating) the threats: some political and technical guidelines for parliamentarians and public officials are identified to improve democratic resilience to prevent and counter foreign interference. A decisive point, while safeguarding fundamental rights and freedoms, is to rethink national security strategies according to the complexity of threats and tools.

² The Independent. (28 July 2018). Final Say: The misinformation that was told about Brexit during and after the referendum. <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/uk/politics/final-say-brexit-referendum-lies-boris-johnson-leave-campaign-remain-a8466751.html>

³ European Center for Populism Studies. (n.d.). Post-truth politics. <https://www.populismstudies.org/Vocabulary/post-truth-politics/>

Introduction

1. The international situation, particularly after the inauguration of the second Trump US Administration, entered an uncharted and chaotic phase of profound transformation and uncertainty, starting with the multilateral system and its institutions: significant developments are occurring all over the world. Among others: the drive of the BRICS+ countries; the importance of the Asian quadrant, and - within it - the role of regional organizations, such as ASEAN, and countries, such as Japan and Australia, in the growing assertiveness of China; the importance of the Gulf countries; new trajectories such as the ‘Cotton Road’ between Europe and India; and the opportunities and risks present in the African continent and in Latin America. The possibility of resolving the ongoing Russian war of aggression against Ukraine, and the conflict in the Middle East, is crucial: with reference to both, the lines of power relations and historical alliances are being rewritten. With reference to Ukraine, the transatlantic axis has entered a crisis: President Trump's approach to Ukrainian President Zelensky has caused an avalanche across the Atlantic. In an unprecedented format, together with Canada, Türkiye, and the Secretary General of NATO, the informal meeting of European leaders in London, on 2 March 2025 (the first of a continuing series), sought to identify a new role for the European Union (EU), in spite of some diverting voices in relation to individual relations with the Kremlin regime. Considering a possible ceasefire between Russia and Ukraine, and the subsequent need for reconstruction and security guarantees of the latter, the current European security requirements impose a new framework of responsibilities on the EU and its Member States (particularly in the fields of security, rearmament and defence) to negotiate, if feasible, a set of transatlantic sustainable agreements. Meanwhile, the decision of the US Secretary of Defence to order the US Cyber Command to withdraw from planning activities against Moscow (including digital offensive actions)⁴ raises new questions: if the ultimate goal of the Trump administration is to separate Russia from China, the biggest risk is that President Putin's Russia will seize the opportunity to feel more ‘protected’ internationally. In this sense, the risks for liberal democracies increase, particularly with regard to disinformation activities and cyber-attacks.
2. In this particularly sensitive global context, characterized by increasing unpredictability, some strategic choices made by States weaken the international system and the resilience of democracies. The suspension of the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) has caused serious problems for humanitarian and development programmes worldwide, in 120 countries. In

⁴ *Exclusive: Hegseth orders Cyber Command to stand down on Russia planning.* (28 February 2025). The Record from Recorded Future News. <https://therecord.media/hegseth-orders-cyber-command-stand-down-russia-planning>

2023, USAID managed approximately \$43.8 billion in aid, all of which was directed to sensitive areas (health, education, economic development, promotion of democracy). Several strategic projects have been halted in vulnerable regions such as Africa, Latin America and Eastern Europe.⁵

3. Ancient history teaches us that propaganda to influence voters is not a new phenomenon. For instance, in the archaeological park of Pompeii, in Italy, inscriptions can be found on the walls of buildings, which survived the eruption of the volcano Vesuvius in 79 AD., referring to and describing certain character attitudes of election candidates. In order to gain trust and votes, candidates relied on influential people who headed electoral committees. Among these inscriptions are *vir bonus et egregius* (a gentleman), *verecundissimus* (very modest), *dignissimus* (very virtuous), *benemerens* (deserving of all good), *frugis* (frugal, honest), *integrus* (upright), and *innocens* (incapable of doing harm).

Figure 1⁶: Political Graffiti, Pompeii, Italy

4. External interference and manipulation activities in a given country have the goal to sway the voters, disrupt democratic processes, and raise fear, chaos, doubt, and division: these activities

⁵ Newsletter European. (19 February 2025). The end of USAID: A turning point for EU international cooperation. <https://www.newslettereuropean.eu/the-end-of-usaid-a-turning-point-for-eu-international-cooperation/>

⁶ Archaeology Magazine. (4 June 2024). Digs & Discoveries - Pompeian Politics - Archaeology Magazine - May/June 2024. Retrieved from <https://archaeology.org/issues/may-june-2024/digs-discoveries/pompeian-politics/>

negatively influence political values, procedures and processes in a democracy, are manipulative in nature, and are usually conducted in a deliberate and coordinated manner. Democracies, the result of a historic achievement to guarantee freedom, fundamental rights and well-being, are under increasing insidious attacks. The cases analyzed in the report, although different in terms of the tools used and the intensity of the attacks, show a clear drift of growing risk for democratic systems. The internal crisis of democratic systems should also be highlighted, with a growing disconnect between institutions, political ruling classes and citizens.

5. One of the most challenging dangers to democratic institutions is manipulation, fake news and disinformation, especially when it is orchestrated by foreign powers. Recent events have shown an increase in aggressive actions by foreign States entities. Additionally, there is an active use of social media, by so-called influencers paid by foreign countries, to support and disseminate false narratives. This report focuses on four States that, based on duly identified and well documented events, represent major threats to democratic systems on a global scale: the Russian Federation, People's Republic of China, Islamic Republic of Iran, and North Korea⁷. It explores: (i) the evolution of disinformation activities and their impact on the resilience of information environment and democratic processes; (ii) foreign interference and cyber-attacks (with recent case studies); and (iii) suggestions and proposals for effective governance of the complexity of the democratic process through appropriate legislation, addressed (in particular) to parliamentarians and public officials. The report also considers how the different threats to democratic systems must be addressed in an integrated manner.

⁷ Bonderud, D. (13 February 2025). Adversarial advantage: using nation-state threat analysis to strengthen US cybersecurity. *Security*. <https://www.ibm.com/think/insights/adversarial-advantage-using-nation-state-threat-analysis-to-strengthen-us-cybersecurity>

Figure 2: A Visual Representation of the Four State Actors and Their Respective Threats to Democratic Systems⁸

6. According to the National Endowment for Democracy report entitled *Winning the Battle of Ideas: Exposing Global Authoritarian Narratives and Revitalizing Democratic Principles* (February 2024)⁹, democracies are in an ideological competition with autocracies that has the potential to reshape the global order. Narratives are a powerful tool of asymmetric power. Authoritarian narratives do not impose the authoritarian model but insist on popularly felt issues, emphasizing the shortcomings of democratic systems. In the present times, liberal democracies struggle to guarantee effective solutions, in the interest of the population, to the planetary challenges that have repercussions at a national level: the constitution (weights and counterweights) of representative democratic systems is under attack from a growing disintermediation, in which polarization, leader-like personalization and lack of strategic vision, risk prevailing. People, increasingly distressed by growing inequalities, seek immediate solutions to concrete problems and rely on the ‘strong man’, rejecting democratic mediations and leaving room for dangerous interference from outside. The National Endowment for Democracy’s report identifies authoritarian narratives in four

⁸ This infographic has been created by the PAM research team, illustrating the threats posed by the Russian Federation, People's Republic of China, Islamic Republic of Iran, and North Korea to democratic systems.

⁹ Staff, F. (15 February 2024). *Winning the Battle of Ideas: Exposing Global Authoritarian Narratives and Revitalizing Democratic Principles* - NATIONAL ENDOWMENT FOR DEMOCRACY. NATIONAL ENDOWMENT FOR DEMOCRACY. <https://www.ned.org/winning-the-battle-of-ideas-exposing-global-authoritarian-narratives-and-revitalizing-democratic-principles/#part-1>

broad categories: (i) non-interference, choice and threats to sovereignty; (ii) exploitation of the grievances of the Global South; (iii) the lack of effectiveness and efficiency of democracies; (iv) the need for a new world order.

7. Not only in the election phase, democratic resilience, is an increasingly strategic element especially in the time of continuous development of AI and emerging technologies. Kevin Frazier notes, for Lawfare (2 January 2025), that although technologies did not disrupt the global electoral landscape in 2024, there are other important elections taking place in 2025 (such as, among others, Belarus, Ecuador, Germany and Australia), and the bar of attention must be kept high. The advancement of AI will increase the intentions of and the opportunities for malicious actors to undermine democratic processes¹⁰.
8. The importance of democratic resilience - in face of growing and interrelated threats – has also been emphasized by NATO Secretary General Mark Rutte at the 2024 NATO Resilience Symposium (12 November 2024) in terms of a whole-of-government and whole-of-society responsibility.¹¹ In an analysis for Chatham House (5 December 2024), Joyce Hakmeh points out that governments must address the evolving threats posed by both state and non-state actors, by adopting a whole-of-society approach and engaging with allies and international partners to adapt to the constantly changing threat landscape. While the risks are real, focusing on resilience-building and addressing current cyber threats will ultimately be more productive than indulging in doomsday scenarios.¹² The President of the Czech Republic, Petr Pavel, in a Keynote Address at the first IISS Prague Defense Summit 2024 (9 November 2024), stressed several important points: (i) We live in an era when threats are neither static nor predictable; (ii) Today, we must be better prepared for the increasingly hybrid nature of these threats, whether they come through conventional military means, cyber-attacks, disinformation campaigns, or tactics designed to destabilize our societies; (iii) we must not overlook the importance and potential of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence, quantum computing, autonomous systems, or advanced cyber capabilities. These will be central to our capability to defend our way of life and our countries¹³.

¹⁰ Frazier, K. (2 January 2025). Why AI did not upend the super year of elections. Default. <https://www.lawfaremedia.org/article/why-ai-did-not-upend-the-super-year-of-elections>

¹¹ Nato. (12 November 2024). Secretary General addresses the 2024 NATO Resilience Symposium. NATO. https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/news_230379.htm

¹² Hakmeh, J. (5 November 2024). Why cyber doomsday warnings do more harm than good. Chatham House. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from: <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2024/11/why-cyber-doomsday-warnings-do-more-harm-good>

¹³ International Institute for Strategic Studies. (9 November 2024). Keynote address. IISS Prague Defence Summit. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://www.iiss.org/events/prague-defence-summit/prague-defence-summit-2024/pds-2024-plenary-sessions/keynote-address/>

9. As the danger and effects of disinformation increasingly pose a global security concern, the US Treasury had incorporated sanctions for foreign actors engaged in these tactics. Specifically, the US Treasury put sanctions on state media organizations and other people involved in disinformation processes. Like, RT and Sputnik International are among the platforms where, among others, fake news finds broad dissemination and the negative impact of supporting Russian military operations has been highlighted: the European Union has also officially banned RT and Sputnik.¹⁴ These sanctions are intended to deny such entities access to funding and reduce their ability to function¹⁵.
10. Disinformation also affects United Nations peacekeeping missions. UN peacekeepers are increasingly confronted with the complexity of the contexts in which they operate, including growing political tensions and disinformation. USG Jean-Pierre Lacroix, Head of UN Peace Operations, addressed this issue on 7 April 2025 at a meeting with the Ambassadors in the Security Council. Lieutenant General Aroldo Lázaro Sáenz, Head of the UN Interim Force in Lebanon (UNIFIL), said on the same occasion that UNIFIL had improved its communication strategy in order to counter disinformation (messages based on facts, clear and coherent). The peace mission in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (MONUSCO) is also committed to combating the disinformation that is used by armed groups to destabilize communities and jeopardize peacekeeping.¹⁶
11. The OECD report (November 2024) Assessing potential future artificial intelligence risks, benefits and policy imperatives places manipulation, misinformation, disinformation, and the consequences for the resilience of democracy, guarantee of fundamental rights and freedoms, rule of law, and social cohesion, among the ten priority risks associated with the development of Artificial Intelligence.¹⁷ Developments in AI systems open threat perspectives to be considered with great attention: spear phishing¹⁸; messages addressed to people on the basis of psychological profiles through ‘personalized persuasion’; ‘compositional deepfakes’¹⁹ that could make it very difficult to

¹⁴ Kayali, L., & Goujard, C. (2 March 2022). EU officially boots Russia’s RT, Sputnik outlets.

Politico. <https://www.politico.eu/article/russia-rt-sputnik-illegal-europe/>

¹⁵ United States Department of State. (13 September 2024). Alerting the world to RT’s global covert activities. State Department. Retrieved from <https://2021-2025.state.gov/alerting-the-world-to-rts-global-covert-activities/>

¹⁶ United Nations. (7 April 2025). UN peacekeeping challenged as conflicts and ceasefires grow more complex. UN News. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://news.un.org/en/story/2025/04/1161976>

¹⁷ Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2024). AI futures. OECD AI Policy Observatory. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://oecd.ai/en/ai-publications/futures>

¹⁸ Spear phishing is a type of phishing attack that targets specific individuals or organizations to gain access to sensitive information or install malware. Spear phishing involves sending fake communications to specific individuals or groups with the aim of inducing targets to install malicious software or hand over confidential information such as usernames, passwords and financial details.

¹⁹ Compositional deepfakes leverage synthetic content in larger disinformation plans that integrate sets of deepfakes over time with observed, expected, and engineered world events to create persuasive synthetic histories. Synthetic histories can be constructed manually but may one day be guided by adversarial generative explanation techniques.

distinguish reality from fiction by creating credible but false narratives. These risks could be exacerbated by anthropomorphized, almost human-like AI systems.

12. Among the most insidious operations, ransomware attacks are increasingly hitting sensitive targets. On 8 November 2024, the United Nations Security Council²⁰ held a hearing during which the Director-General of the World Health Organization (WHO) insisted on the grave danger that ransomware attacks pose to national and international healthcare systems and data protection as a fundamental aspect of international security.
13. AI and machine learning have given even more strength to malicious offensive capabilities and quantum computing may open new frontiers in the cybersecurity landscape²¹. Synthetic products made by artificial intelligence are becoming increasingly sophisticated. AI is a ‘two-faced Janus’ technology because it has both the ability to amplify disinformation on strategic policy issues and to manipulate a wide audience. At the same time, the technology itself has the capacity to counter such negative drifts. AI-generated disinformation (which could challenge the basic principles of democracy and science) is a sensitive concern for democratic institutions and the scientific community (think, for example, of the anti-vaccine campaign experienced during the Covid-19 pandemic).
14. AI-generated disinformation has a strong impact on the information ecosystem: hence, in order to strengthen democratic systems resilience, the issue of ‘information integrity’ (concept referring to the accuracy, consistency, and reliability of information) as elaborated in the UN Global Principles for Information Integrity is of particular importance²².
15. The importance of blockchain technology, and cryptocurrencies as its most prominent use case, is well established by both attackers and defenders. For example, Russian ransomware gangs and North Korean hackers use the decentralized and anonymous nature of cryptocurrencies to generate revenue, launder money, evade sanctions and conduct illicit activities.²³ This became widely known after the US Treasury Department accused Russian state media employees of funding a

²⁰ United Nations. (8 November 2024). Ransomware attacks on healthcare sector ‘pose a direct and systemic risk to global public health and security’. UN Press. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://press.un.org/en/2024/sc15891.doc.htm>

²¹ The Soufan Center. (15 November 2024). Quantum computing and the evolving cyber threat landscape. IntelBrief. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://thesoufancenter.org/intelbrief-2024-november-15/>

²² United Nations. (n.d.). Global principles for information integrity. United Nations. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://www.un.org/en/information-integrity/global-principles>

²³ Raman, S. (17 October 2024). Blockchain intelligence and the emerging geopolitics of crypto. Binding Hook. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://bindinghook.com/articles-hooked-on-trends/blockchain-intelligence-and-the-emerging-geopolitics-of-crypto/>

Tennessee-based company to the tune of around \$10 million. This company was involved in the production and dissemination of fake American media that was propaganda for Russia²⁴.

16. The competitive battle between democracies and autocracies over emerging technologies affects national security issues. An interesting case concerns LiDAR, a remote sensing technology with both military and civilian applications. Craig Singleton and Mark Montgomery write about it for the think tank Foundation for Defense of Democracies (2 December 2024): Today, Chinese companies are rapidly consolidating control over the global LiDAR market, with PRC-origin sensors now widely deployed across civilian and military networks worldwide, including in the United States. These sensors often serve as essential nodes within interconnected public safety, transportation, and utility systems, which is a clear benefit to the United States. However, Chinese LiDAR's system-wide integration also leaves its users vulnerable to espionage and sabotage, potentially enabling Beijing to access sensitive U.S. data or disrupt critical operations²⁵.
17. People live immersed within the digital space, and it is crucial to work to ensure that this space is open and safe, as well as respects, protects and promotes human rights. The UN Pact for the Future, Global Digital Compact and Declaration on Future Generations, adopted at the UN Summit of the Future (September 2024), indicate that: We [UN Member States] commit to respect, protect and promote human rights in the digital space. We will uphold international human rights law throughout the life cycle of digital and emerging technologies so that users can safely benefit from digital technologies and are protected from violations, abuses and all forms of discrimination. We recognize the responsibilities of all stakeholders in this endeavor and also call on the private sector to apply the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights. Deutsche Welle, on 22 September 2024, emphasized how the Russian Federation, at the very last minute, attempted to boycott the approval of the Pact. After the adoption of the Pact by the vast majority of UN Member States, the Russian Ambassador to the UN in NY, Dmitry Polyanskiy, in a post on X, called it 'unbalanced'. It should be noted that Russia's objections were only supported by its allies Belarus, North Korea, Iran, Nicaragua and Syria.²⁶
18. From a political and strategic perspective, the role of all nations in shaping global digital standards and rules has been increasingly emphasized. Within this context, initiatives from African and Mediterranean regions have been highlighted for their contributions to civic technology and

²⁴ BBC News. (13 April 2025). The impact of AI on global economies. BBC News. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c8rx28v1vpro>

²⁵ Singleton, C., & Montgomery, M. (2 December 2024). Laser focus: Countering China's LiDAR threat to U.S. critical infrastructure and military systems. Foundation for Defense of Democracies. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://www.fdd.org/analysis/2024/12/02/laser-focus-countering-chinas-lidar-threat-to-u-s-critical-infrastructure-and-military-systems/>

²⁶ Deutsche Welle. (22 September 2024). UN reform plan adopted despite Russian opposition. DW. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://www.dw.com/en/un-reform-plan-adopted-despite-russian-opposition/a-70295441>

governance, often serving as illustrative examples of democratic innovation. Efforts have also been made to ensure fair representation of these regions in international discussions on artificial intelligence and digital policy. In addition, Euro-Mediterranean-African cooperation has been encouraged to jointly develop resilience strategies that reflect regional needs and shared interests.

19. On 21 September 2024, at the eve of the UN Summit of the Future, PAM, held a high-level parliamentary event, Parliamentary Support in Re-Establishing Trust and Reputation in Multilateral Governance (with the support of the PAM Centre for Global Studies (CGS), and in partnership with the UN Security Council Counter-Terrorism Executive Directorate (CTED) and the Permanent Missions of the Kingdom of Morocco and Italy to the UN²⁷.

Foreign Interference: disinformation and cyber attacks

Disinformation

20. The Secretary General of the United Nations wrote in the report ‘Countering disinformation for the promotion and protection of human rights and fundamental freedom’ (12 August 2022 - citing the International Telecommunication Union and the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, UNESCO), that the term disinformation can be used to describe false or misleading content that can cause specific harm, irrespective of motivations, awareness or behaviors²⁸. Disinformation permeates all areas of personal and social life. Identity-based disinformation spreads misleading or false claims about gender, sexuality, race, ethnicity, religion and other identity markers: disinformation is a broad-based malicious activity that encompasses, among other things, climate change, migration, health, nutrition, and elections. The aim is to undermine the dignity of the most vulnerable targets. Disinformation destabilizes social cohesion, progressively undermines trust in democratic processes and works on social vulnerabilities to gain strategic advantage. It is not just a matter of disinformation but, through this, of weakening democratic structures by targeting social groups, spreading fear and exacerbating divisions. During the research project, a critical approach to the cognitive and social mechanisms underlying disinformation phenomena will be proposed. Disinformation is an ancient phenomenon, but it is with the ongoing development of emerging technologies that it has become more pervasive. As Ann M. Fitzgerald and Halyna Padalko (RUSI, 25 July 2024) note²⁹, there is a need to work

²⁷ Parliamentary Assembly of the Mediterranean. (21 September 2024). High-level parliamentary event at the UN Summit of the Future. PAM. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://pam.int/pam-high-level-parliamentary-event-at-the-un-summit-of-the-future/>

²⁸ United Nations. (n.d.). Countering disinformation. United Nations. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://www.un.org/en/countering-disinformation>

²⁹ Fitz-Gerald, A. M., & Padalko, H. (25 July 2024). The need for a strategic approach to disinformation and AI-driven threats. Royal United Services Institute. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://www.rusi.org/explore-our-research/publications/commentary/need-strategic-approach-disinformation-and-ai-driven-threats>

effectively on threats in the information domain: the development of AI has exacerbated the creation and spread of disinformation in the online environment.

21. Among other strategies, disinformation is implemented through: (i) clickbait: sensational headlines and stories to attract clicks; (ii) memetic warfare: viral memes (simple, shareable, emotional) to quickly spread disinformation; (iii) astroturfing: false grassroots reality campaigns sponsored by covert organizations; (iv) propaganda: deliberate activities, in many cases state-sponsored, to disseminate distorted or misleading information.

Figure 3: A Flowchart Showing the Main Ways in Which Disinformation is Carried Out and Its Effects on Society³⁰

22. AI is very efficient in producing fake news articles, videos, and social media posts that are suitable for manipulation. Such AI-generated contents look authentic, and ordinary people would find it hard to differentiate between real and fake information.

³⁰ This infographic has been created by the PAM research team, illustrating the main ways in which disinformation is carried out (clickbait, memetic warfare, astroturfing, propaganda) and the environment in which disinformation produces its effects (information bubbles, gaslighting, deliberate attempts to divide society).

23. Deepfake audios and videos can present the specific public figures saying or acting in ways they never actually were, which may mislead the audience. Among others, French President Macron³¹ and US Secretary of State Marc Rubio have been affected by this.³²
24. A strategic focus is on Africa: artificial intelligence and emerging technologies are very active in undermining or strengthening people's trust in electoral processes (many elections are scheduled across the continent between 2025 and 2027). It is crucial to emphasize the importance of ethical and inclusive governance of AI and emerging technologies for the African context, where elections take place in contexts characterized by fragile peace, ethnic divisions and low trust in institutions: regional initiatives such as the African Union's Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa (2020-2030)³⁴ help to root such governance efforts in African realities.
25. AI and QAnon Disinformation in Elections: The New York Times has reported that AI is being used to create and disseminate fake news, especially ahead of the United States of America elections. It is crucial to see that deepfakes and AI-generated text have been employed to spread conspiracy theories, like QAnon. This is a conspiracy theory that originated from the alt-right in the fall of 2017. It alleges that a secret group of Satan-worshipping pedophiles is running a global child sex-trafficking ring and conspiring against President Donald Trump³⁵. It started with posts on the anonymous site 4chan by a user named "Q," who claims to own high-level government access. The FBI decided to recognize QAnon as a type of 'domestic terrorism threat' due to its efforts to incite violence³⁶. Furthermore, such complex techniques of misinformation are intended to influence voters' perception of reality and cause division among them. The incorporation of AI campaigns can therefore be viewed as a progression in the tools used to manipulate democratic activities³⁷.
26. It is interesting to point out at some tools through which disinformation activities produce their distorting effects: (i) information bubbles: algorithms focus on amplifying the confirmatory biases of increasingly isolated individuals in information environments that reinforce their opinions (e.g.:

³¹ Marie-Courtois, T. (26 September 2023). Beware of this deepfake about the alleged resignation of Emmanuel Macron. AFP Factual. Retrieved from: <https://factuel.afp.com/doc.afp.com.33WK8PE>

³² dpa. (12 March 2024). Emmanuel Macron et France 24 victims of a deepfake. dpa-Factchecking. <https://dpa-factchecking.com/belgium/240311-99-298903/>

³³ Interesting Engineering. (9 July 2025). 'Fake': Marco Rubio's AI clone tries to scam politicians using Signal. Interesting Engineering. <https://interestingengineering.com/culture/marco-rubio-fake-ai-clone-scam>

³⁴ African Union. (18 May 2020). Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa (2020–2030). <https://au.int/en/documents/20200518/digital-transformation-strategy-africa-2020-2030>

³⁵ Roose, K. (15 July 2024). What is QAnon? The New York Times. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://www.nytimes.com/article/what-is-qanon.html>

³⁶ BBC News. (20 July 2020). QAnon: What is it and where did it come from? BBC News. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://www.bbc.com/news/53498434>

³⁷ Roose, K. (17 September 2024). Election AI and QAnon disinformation. The New York Times. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://www.nytimes.com/2024/09/17/technology/election-ai-qanon-disinformation.html>

political disinformation through social media that reinforces polarized opinions); (ii) gaslighting: manipulative tactics that lead people to problematize their perception of reality (e.g.: denying clear facts, such as election results, to create confusion and doubt); deliberate attempts to divide society: this is done through the dissemination of false political narratives or identity-based disinformation (e.g.: disinformation aimed at creating tensions and polarizing society by targeting particular ethnic or religious groups to inflame tensions).

27. According to the US Government Accountability Office (GAO) (26 September 2024)³⁸, the main foreign governments that have spread most of the disinformation over the years are the Russian Federation, the People's Republic of China, and the Islamic Republic of Iran: the aim of these countries is to increase their strategic influence³⁹.

Russian Federation

28. In a joint article for the Financial Times⁴⁰ dated September 2024, the heads of the CIA and MI6 described Russian intelligence activity as a reckless campaign of sabotage across Europe, noting that Russia's use of technology to spread lies and disinformation is designed to sow division. In January 2022⁴¹ identified five methods through which the Russian Federation spreads disinformation: official government communications; state-funded messaging (RT and Sputnik); the use of social media as a weapon; cyber techniques, such as 'spoofed' websites posing as legitimate websites; and websites run by organizations or individuals that may have covert ties to Russia. For example, the Russian Federation, in an attempt to undermine global support for Ukraine, following its failed war of aggression against the country, disseminated pro-Russian disinformation to local media in Latin America, which then published the information as if it had originated locally. Clemson University's Media Forensics Hub reported that posts by DC Weekly, identified by the U.S. Department of Homeland Security as a Russian disinformation and propaganda tool, spread the fake news that Ukrainian President Zelensky and his wife were

³⁸ U.S. Government Accountability Office. (26 September 2024). Foreign disinformation: Defining and detecting threats. GAO. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from: <https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-24-107600>

³⁹ Digital Forensic Research Lab. (29 February 2024). Undermining Ukraine: How Russia widened its global information war in 2023. Atlantic Council. Retrieved 13 April 2025, from <https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/in-depth-research-reports/report/undermining-ukraine-how-russia-widened-its-global-information-war-in-2023/>

⁴⁰ Financial Times. (7 September 2024). Get Started | Republishing | FT Professional. Financial Times. <https://www.ft.com/content/252d7cc6-27de-46c0-9697-f3eb04888e70>

⁴¹ United States Department of State. (24 January, 2022). GEC Special Report: Russia's pillars of disinformation and propaganda. State Department. Retrieved from <https://2021-2025.state.gov/russias-pillars-of-disinformation-and-propaganda-report/>

misusing foreign aid to enrich themselves: notably, a DC Weekly article falsely claimed that Zelensky had used American aid money to buy two yachts⁴².

29. Electoral disinformation risks destabilizing the democratic processes by working to distort the information landscape and create confusion among voters. A case in point is Operation Doppelganger⁴³, put in charge by Russian malicious actors. These are hybrid warfare tools deployed by state and non-state actors to destabilize political systems and influence foreign policy.
30. According to the report Locking Down the Windows (JX Fund, 25 September 2024)⁴⁴, Russian Federation established in 2024 a budget of around 660 million euros over five years to control the country's digital space. Independent Russian media in exile are a vital line of defense: news outlets such as Meduza operated from abroad for years before Russia's illegal large-scale invasion of Ukraine. After 2022, a diverse range of media joined the exile movement, including smaller investigative platforms, specialized news providers focused on Telegram, regional outlets and various YouTube projects. In 2024, Russia strengthened AI-based censorship techniques, intensified repression of independent journalism, VPN blocks, and hindered access to content on platforms such as YouTube and Telegram.
31. On 11 September 2024 the Russian government published the 'Strategy of State Cultural Policy', which focuses on the need to take measures to protect Russian traditional values from Western influence. Among the 'truths' told is the story of the Ukrainian theatre in Mariupol, which, according to Russia, was severely damaged by the Ukrainian Army. This is a case of disinformation: the claim is false. In fact, Ukraine used the Mariupol theatre as an air raid shelter, with the word 'Children' painted in large white letters on an open-air floor space. Russian army bombed and destroyed the theatre on 16 March 2022, causing hundreds of Ukrainian civilian casualties. This incident is described in the report of the Independent International Commission of Inquiry on Ukraine, which conducts a detailed investigation of the events and indicates the actions of Russian forces as war crimes⁴⁵.
32. Leonid Martynyuk (Voice of America, 29 October 2024) reported⁴⁶ that on 24 October, at a press conference in Kazan, Russian President Putin replied to an NBC News correspondent, who had

⁴² BBC News. (21 December 2023). How pro-Russian 'yacht' propaganda influenced US debate over Ukraine aid. BBC News. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-us-canada-67766964>

⁴³ EU DisinfoLab. (September 2024). Doppelganger operation. EU DisinfoLab. <https://www.disinfo.eu/doppelganger-operation/>

⁴⁴ Study "Locking down the windows." (2024). Retrieved from <https://jx-fund.org/newsroom/news/study-locking-down-the-windows/>

⁴⁵ UN Human Rights Council. (15 March 2024). Report of the Independent International Commission of Inquiry on Ukraine (A/HRC/55/66) [Advance unedited version]. ReliefWeb. <https://reliefweb.int/report/ukraine/report-independent-international-commission-inquiry-ukraine-ahrc5566-advance-unedited-version-enruuk>

⁴⁶ Martynyuk, L. (29 October 2024). Putin claims, falsely, US, not Russia, escalated situation in Ukraine. VOA News. <https://www.voanews.com/a/putin-claims-falsely-us-not-russia-escalated-situation-in-ukraine/7843445.html>

asked him if the participation of North Korean troops in the war in Ukraine was an escalation. Putin replied that the escalation began with the 2014 coup, which he claimed was financed by the United States: this is a false narrative that the Kremlin has been using for about a decade and which originates from the distortion of a statement by Victoria Nuland (made at a conference organized by the think tanks of the U.S. -Ukraine Foundation on 13 December 2013), former assistant to the US Secretary of State. The 2014 Ukrainian revolution, also known as Euromaidan, was a series of protests and political events that led to the ousting of President Viktor Yanukovich, widely considered corrupt and oppressive. This narrative is part of the propaganda campaign introduced by the Kremlin to justify the illegal war of aggression against Ukraine. The European Parliament, in order to condemn Moscow's systematic use of historical arguments, falsification and disinformation to justify the war against Ukraine, on 23 January 2025 adopted an ad hoc resolution.⁴⁷

33. The Russian Federation used the decision of the US mainstream media (more than 200, including the Washington Post, the Los Angeles Times, and USA Today) not to endorse any candidate in the 5 November US presidential election to underline the Kremlin's influence on the American press. In Russia, Maria Zakharova, spokesperson for the Russian Foreign Ministry, said the decision was made because both candidates were branded with a 'Russian stamp'. Zakharova wrote on her Telegram channel (29 October 2029): American newspapers, the bigwigs of the media business, refuse to support any candidate in the U.S. elections one after another. This time they cannot support anyone, because both have the stamp 'Russian.' The American media industry itself appointed Trump as such [labelled Trump as pro-Russian], having been making up fables for almost 10 years. And [Russian President Vladimir] Putin promised to support Harris' candidacy. That is why the information mainstream in the States has been torn apart. Leonid Martynyuk (Voice of America, 1 November 2024) reported⁴⁸.
34. Meta's and YouTube's Actions Against Russian Disinformation: Meta blocked Russian state media outlets such as RT, this is a massive step to limit where disinformation can proliferate. The news follows on from these continuing attempts to influence public opinion through social media by Russian entities. Likewise, YouTube has removed more than 230 channels linked to Russian state media, such as RT and Sputnik, because of United States of America government sanctions. The

⁴⁷ European Parliament. (23 January 2025). MEPs condemn Russia's use of disinformation to justify its war in Ukraine. European Parliament. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20250116IPR26330/meps-condemn-russia-s-use-of-disinformation-to-justify-its-war-in-ukraine>

⁴⁸ Martynyuk, L. (1 November 2024). Moscow claims, falsely, that US media are refusing to endorse presidential candidates due to 'Russian stamp'. VOA News. <https://www.voanews.com/a/moscow-claims-falsely-that-us-media-are-refusing-to-endorse-presidential-candidates-due-to-russian-stamp-/7848128.html>

moves are a part of wider-ranging actions by tech companies to stem the tide of disinformation and protect democratic processes against manipulation⁴⁹.

35. Russian President Putin told the Valdai International Club (7 November 2024) that Ukraine provoked Moscow to go to war. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, under the Belovezha Accords, Russia accepted Ukraine's borders and revoked its neutrality status. Later, Putin said, this neutrality had disappeared with Ukraine's announced desire to join NATO. This would lead to non-acceptance by Moscow, as Leonid Martynyuk (Voice of America, 12 November 2024) reported⁵⁰.
36. Disinformation is a key part of the hybrid warfare the Russian Federation has unleashed in Africa. The Africa Defense Forum magazine stated that Russia is linked to 40 per cent of disinformation campaigns on the African continent. Russian President Putin asserted that Russia has never engaged in any inhumane activities on the African continent: on 7 November 2024, during the Valdai International Discussion Club, Putin said: In the history of our relations with the African continent, there has never been any shadow - never; we have never exploited African peoples, nor been engaged in anything inhuman on the African continent. Purity Mwambia (Voice of America, 14 November 2024) reported⁵¹.

People's Republic of China

37. GEC⁵² emphasizes the five main methods of the PRC's approach: propaganda and censorship; promotion of Chinese surveillance technology, information control and governance norms of digital platforms in line with PRC preferences; utilizing international organizations and bilateral partnerships; engaging prominent individuals in order to align their views with China's narratives; and controlling Chinese-language media (China Media Group, People's Daily and Xinhua). According to GEC, PRC employs: bots, software applications that perform automated tasks on the Internet (such as large-scale messaging), to mimic human activities; Internet trolls, individuals who post messages online to distract from an online discussion or to provoke fear and anger; fake social media accounts, and 'flooding', to manipulate search engine results and hashtag searches.

⁴⁹ Conger, K. (17 September 2024). Meta blocks RT, Russian state TV, from its platforms. The New York Times. <https://www.nytimes.com/2024/09/17/technology/meta-rt-russian-tv.html>

⁵⁰ Martynyuk, L. (12 November 2024). Putin justifies war in Ukraine by accusing Kyiv of violating a treaty Moscow violated repeatedly. VOA News. <https://www.voanews.com/a/putin-justifies-war-in-ukraine-by-accusing-kyiv-of-violating-a-treaty-moscow-violated-repeatedly/7861987.html>

⁵¹ Mwambia, P. (14 November 2024). Putin attempts whitewashing Russian atrocities in Africa. VOA News. <https://www.voanews.com/a/putin-attempts-whitewashing-russian-atrocities-in-africa-/7864339.html>

⁵² United States Department of State. (23 February, 2024). How the People's Republic of China Seeks to Reshape the Global Information Environment. State Department. Retrieved from <https://2021-2025.state.gov/gec-special-report-how-the-peoples-republic-of-china-seeks-to-reshape-the-global-information-environment/>

38. Google removed hundreds of news sites and domains from Google News for disseminating pro-China content. In a report by Google's Threat Analysis Group and Mandiant⁵³, Seeing Through a GLASSBRIDGE: Understanding the Digital Marketing Ecosystem Spreading Pro-PRC Influence Operations, Glassbridge's operations by four China-based companies (Shanghai Haixun Technology, Times Newswire, Duribridge, and Shenzhen Bowen Media) operating inauthentic news sites and newswire services are outlined. The actors of the news operations, posing as independent and often local news organizations, adapted their content to a specific regional audience, presenting their narratives as apparently legitimate news and editorial content. The researchers stated that they observed similar behavior in Russian and Iranian campaigns. Investigators found inauthentic news domain names targeting countries in Eastern Europe, the Middle East, Africa, Asia, and the United States, specifically targeting some content to the Chinese-speaking diaspora. Among the content examined, some came from Dragonbridge⁵⁴, another influencer operation Google has been targeting for the past three years. Since 2022, Google has published several reports on China's efforts to create fake news websites⁵⁵ and YouTube channels to promote pro-government narratives, as⁵⁶ Jonathan Greig (The Report, 22 November 2024) reported⁵⁷.

Islamic Republic of Iran

39. The Office of the Director of US National Intelligence (ODNI)⁵⁸ released a statement (15 May 2024) outlining how Iran is increasingly aggressive (using social media, influencers, and state-controlled media) in an attempt to spread disinformation and erode trust in American democratic institutions. The US Agency for Global Media pointed out that Iran's state-controlled Press TV, in English and French, and Hispan TV, in Spanish, target foreign audiences to promote narratives from Iran's point of view.

⁵³ Molter, V. (22 November 2024). Seeing through a GLASSBRIDGE: Understanding the digital marketing ecosystem spreading pro-PRC influence operations. Google Cloud. <https://cloud.google.com/blog/topics/threat-intelligence/glassbridge-pro-prc-influence-operations>

⁵⁴ Janofsky, A. (4 August 2022). Pro-China information campaign used fake websites to spread propaganda: Mandiant. The Record. <https://therecord.media/pro-china-information-campaign-used-fake-websites-to-spread-propaganda-mandiant>

⁵⁵ Peterson, A. (26 October 2022). Report: Pro-China influence operation targeted U.S. midterms. The Record. <https://therecord.media/report-pro-china-influence-operation-targeted-u-s-midterms>

⁵⁶ Greig, J. (26 January 2023). Google shut down thousands of pro-Beijing disinformation channels on Taiwan, COVID-19. The Record. <https://therecord.media/google-shut-down-thousands-of-pro-chinese-govt-disinformation-channels-on-taiwan-covid-19>

⁵⁷ Greig, J. (22 November 2024). Google takes down fake news sites, wire services run by Chinese influence operation. The Record. <https://therecord.media/google-fake-news-china-outlets>

⁵⁸ Haines, A. (15 May 2024). DNI Haines opening statement as delivered to the SSCI for an update on foreign threats to the 2024 elections. Office of the Director of National Intelligence. <https://www.odni.gov/index.php/newsroom/congressional-testimonies/congressional-testimonies-2024/3823-dni-haines-opening-statement-as-delivered-to-the-ssci-for-an-update-on-foreign-threats-to-the-2024-elections>

Disinformation in Africa

40. African countries are not only affected by foreign disinformation, but also serve as environments where protest, innovation, and democratic experimentation emerge. Internal disinformation dynamics, which may precede or intensify foreign influence campaigns, have drawn increasing attention. Local civic initiatives such as election observation platforms (GuineaVote), fact-checking projects (Africa Check⁵⁹, Désinfox Afrique⁶⁰) and digital literacy efforts play a key role in strengthening societal resilience. Nonetheless, structural inequalities including weak public institutions, limited access to reliable information, and low levels of digital literacy continue to create vulnerabilities that enhance the impact of disinformation.
41. According to the Africa Center for Strategic Studies (13 March 2024)⁶¹, disinformation campaigns aimed at manipulating African information systems have almost quadrupled since 2022: this has had destabilizing consequences for the (very often fragile) democratic processes on the continent. External interference involves 23 transnational disinformation campaigns. Russia (with 16 operations that can be traced back to it) and China take center stage. In addition to promoting their own global interests, they fuel coups, increase anti-Western and anti-United Nations sentiments, and spread disinformation about climate change. Paid African influencers, digital avatars and fake information material amplify Russian-controlled communications so that disinformation narratives become mechanical. A network of African organizations (Partenariat Alternatif Russie-Afrique pour le Développement Économique and Groupe Panafric in pour le Commerce et l'Investissement), probably with the involvement of Russian embassies, serve to create and amplify disinformation. After the death in 2023 of Yevgeny Prigozhin, founder of the Russian-mercenary Wagner Group, Russian disinformation operations are in the hands of the Russian Africa Corps and the Africa Initiative News Agency, which are directly linked to the Russian Ministry of Defense and intelligence services.
42. The Chinese Communist Party (CCP), through the United Front and China Media Group, ranks second in terms of disinformation in Africa. The CCP, in order to increase the use of disinformation, has a more institutionalized approach⁶² and recycles its official narratives through ownership and control of ICT infrastructure, as well as through licensing and training agreements with African media.

⁵⁹ Africa Check. (5 June 2025). Sorting fact from fiction. <https://africacheck.org/>

⁶⁰ CFI. (2024). Désinfox Afrique. <https://cfi.fr/fr/projet/desinfox-afrique>

⁶¹ Africa Center for Strategic Studies. (13 March 2024). Mapping a surge of disinformation in Africa. Africa Center for Strategic Studies. <https://africacenter.org/spotlight/mapping-a-surge-of-disinformation-in-africa/>

⁶² Africa Center for Strategic Studies. (12 May 2023). China's influence on African media. Africa Center for Strategic Studies. <https://africacenter.org/spotlight/chinas-influence-on-african-media/>

43. The Sahel area is a very interesting case study: it is a particularly sensitive region from a geopolitical and geo-economic point of view. It is often remembered for demographic issues, terrorism, conflicts, military coups, human and drug trafficking: in the region, state and non-state actors engage in various forms of communication to influence circumstances. PAM attended on 23 and 24 October 2024, the two-day event on ‘Russian, Chinese and Other Misinformation and Disinformation Efforts in the Sahel Region’ (organized in Naples by the Supreme Allied Commander Transformation and the NATO Strategic Direction-South HUB)⁶³. Russia and China, especially after the withdrawal of France and the United States military presence, are increasingly becoming key players⁶⁴: the two countries are focused on shaping the media and information landscapes through disruption, in order to serve their own strategic goals and interests.
44. With regard to Russia’s role in the Sahel area, disinformation activities have been of great importance. Russian-based disinformation centers run a series of social media channels that spread pro-Russian and anti-Western content in the Sahel. The African Initiative⁶⁵, a new version of the Prigozhin-era disinformation operations, is strategic for Russia. Russia’s objectives in the Sahel, in the more general context of hybrid warfare⁶⁶, are to build global influence and reduce Western interests. Countries like Mali and the Central African Republic are interesting to analyze, where Russia has provided security assistance, diplomatic support and help with intelligence operations.
45. China has a more institutionalized approach in the Sahel: decisive is China ability to dominate telecommunication networks, many of which were built or strengthened by Chinese companies as part of the Belt and Road Initiative. This infrastructure allows state-owned Chinese media, such as Xinhua and CGTN (China Global Television Network), to collaborate with local media, thereby influencing the content disseminated, ensuring the dominance of pro-Chinese narratives.
46. The Commander of the US Africa Command (AFRICOM), Gen. Michael Langley⁶⁷, as published by Al Arabiya on 12 September 2024, said that the campaigns of Russia and China are fueling strong instability in civil society and some armed forces in Africa. Langley emphasized, with a focus on the Sahel and the fight against terrorism, that this has been distorted by Russian activities

⁶³ Open Perspectives Exchange Network. (23 October 2024). OPEN Study Day 2024: Final Report. Issuu. https://issuu.com/spp_plp/docs/open_study_day_final_report?fr=xKAE9_zU1NQ

⁶⁴ NATO Strategic Direction-South Hub. (November 2024). Russian, Chinese, and other disinformation and misinformation efforts in the Sahel. The Southern Hub. <https://thesouthernhub.org/topics/technology-innovation/russian-chinese-and-other-disinformation-and-misinformation-efforts-in-the-sahel>

⁶⁵ ADF Staff. (8 October 2024). ‘African Initiative,’ a new Russian media outlet, promotes disinformation. Africa Defense Forum. <https://adf-magazine.com/2024/10/african-initiative-a-new-russian-media-outlet-promotes-disinformation/>

⁶⁶ Bilal, A. (26 April 2024). Russia’s hybrid war against the West. NATO Review. <https://www.nato.int/docu/review/articles/2024/04/26/russias-hybrid-war-against-the-west/index.html>

⁶⁷ Al Arabiya English. (12 September 2024). Russia and China are spreading misinformation across Sahel: Top US general for Africa. Al Arabiya. <https://english.alarabiya.net/News/united-states/2024/09/12/russia-and-china-are-spreading-misinformation-across-sahel-top-us-general-for-africa>

in the information space. The General criticized the negative impact of this Russian activity in the Central African Republic to Libya and throughout the Sahel. Regarding China, Langley reiterated how Beijing is also known to spread misinformation and disinformation throughout the African continent.

Figure 4: A Map Showing the Surge of Disinformation Campaigns in Africa and the Sahel Region⁶⁸

Mapping a Surge Disinformation in Africa

Countering disinformation

47. On 12 August 2022, the Secretary-General of the United Nations submitted to the General Assembly the report ‘Countering disinformation for the promotion and protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms’⁶⁹. The introduction states: “Current discussions on disinformation

⁶⁸ This infographic has been created by the PAM research team, illustrating the surge of disinformation campaigns in Africa and the Sahel area, highlighting the primary state sponsors, the impact on stability, and the digital expansion in the region. Data sourced from the Africa Center for Strategic Studies (2024): Mapping a Surge of Disinformation in Africa: <https://africacenter.org/spotlight/mapping-a-surge-of-disinformation-in-africa/#Data>

⁶⁹ United Nations. (n.d.). Countering Disinformation | United Nations. Retrieved from <https://www.un.org/en/countering-disinformation>

reflect a new and rapidly evolving communications landscape, in part due to innovative technologies that enable the dissemination of unparalleled volumes of content at unprecedented speeds. Navigating this modern and qualitatively different media landscape and ensuring it advances, rather than undermines, the protection and promotion of human rights and international peace and security is a key challenge of our time”.

48. Since January 2018, with a report entitled “A multi-dimensional approach to disinformation”, the European Commission has been working on the issue of combating disinformation with a multi-dimensional and multi-stakeholder approach.⁷⁰
49. Bateman and Dean Jackson, in the report *Countering Disinformation Effectively: An Evidence-Based Policy Guide* (Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 31 January 2024)⁷¹, draw a complex framework of solutions against disinformation. In fact, it is not limited to the realm of new technologies and social media but covers a much wider range of areas: education, journalism and political institutions. Responding to disinformation requires both tactical (fact-checking and labelling of social media content) and strategic actions over the medium to long term (support for local journalism and digital literacy), with an ongoing verification process. Counter-disinformation policies are not resolved in the short term: merely tactical actions (such as announcements of the discovery or disruption of malicious networks) have limited impact. Major investments are needed in the strategic research infrastructure: human capital, access to data and technology. The study of disinformation must become more comprehensive and robust. From the point of view of ordinary citizens, who must distinguish between what is true and what is false, decisive factors, in addition to the credibility of the content, are the repetition of messages, narrative appeal, perceived authority, group identification and the mood of the viewer.
50. In contexts such as Africa, particular attention must be paid to media literacy, civic education and the protection of independent journalism as part of democratic resilience: in many African countries, democratic resilience is civic rather than digital. Adequate resilience policies must consider long-term investment in civic education and media literacy, particularly among young people, rural populations and first-time voters; strengthening independent media and local journalism, which often constitute the first line of defense against disinformation; protecting digital

⁷⁰ European Political Strategy Centre. (25 April 2018). The age of artificial intelligence: Towards a European strategy for human-centric machines. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/6ef4df8b-4cea-11e8-be1d-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁷¹ Bateman, J., & Jackson, D. (31 January 2024). *Countering disinformation effectively: An evidence-based policy guide*. Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2024/01/countering-disinformation-effectively-an-evidence-based-policy-guide?lang=en>

rights defenders and journalists, many of whom are increasingly targeted by foreign and domestic actors.

Cyber Attacks

51. According to Google Cloud Security’s Cybersecurity Forecast 2025 report⁷², published on 13 November 2024, malicious actors are expected to continue using AI-based tools for their purposes in 2025: phishing attacks⁷³, vishing⁷⁴, SMS, identity theft deepfakes, fraud, and circumvention of KYC (Know Your Customer) security requirements⁷⁵. According to the report, the demand for Large Language Models (LLMs) will grow in underground forums that have no security barriers. The use of LLMs will also support content creation and the production of seemingly authentic articles published on non-authentic websites. From the defenders’ point of view, the use of AI as a tool to counter malicious attacks and to ensure security will enter a second phase in 2025: an intermediate phase of semi-autonomous operations will begin, requiring human intervention.
52. The already mentioned Google Cloud Security’s Cybersecurity Forecast 2025 report predicts that malicious actors in the Russian Federation, People’s Republic of China, Islamic Republic of Iran, and North Korea will continue to use tactics and hit established targets. In particular: (i) Russia will focus many of its malicious attacks on the conflict front in Ukraine (in 2024, analysts observed attacks on critical infrastructure and the use of hacktivist groups such as Cyber Army of Russia Reborn⁷⁶): furthermore, the country will continue to support its global interests by targeting governments, politicians, civil society, journalists, media and technology organizations mainly in Europe and NATO member states, including high-profile events as seen with the Paris 2024 Olympics⁷⁷; (ii) Chinese malicious actors will continue to use ‘stealthy tactics’ (ORB networks,

⁷² Greenberg, A. (13 November 2024). Emerging threats: Cybersecurity forecast 2025. Google Cloud. <https://cloud.google.com/blog/topics/threat-intelligence/cybersecurity-forecast-2025>

⁷³ Phishing attacks are a type of cyberattack that use fraudulent emails, text messages, phone calls, or websites to trick people into sharing sensitive data or downloading malware. They are a form of social engineering.

⁷⁴ Vishing is a form of scam similar to phishing, with the aim of deceptively stealing private information. The scam exploits and automates the persuasion typical of social engineering techniques and is carried out via telephone services. In particular, the attackers make phone calls by simulating the existence of a call center (of a bank, for instance) and asking the victim to give their details to an operator. Unlike classic phishing (via e-mail), vishing exploits the increased trust that humans tend to place in a person who appears to be authorized to request such information.

⁷⁵ KYC or Know Your Customer is the process that financial institutions and other businesses use to ascertain the identity of their customers, ensuring they are who they claim to be. The main objective of KYC is to verify customer’s identities, ensure compliance with regulations, and mitigate risks with money laundering and terrorist financing. The four objectives of KYC are customer identification, risk management, regulatory compliance, and trust building to prevent financial crimes and ensure the economic system’s integrity. The KYC process is essential to prevent financial fraud, money laundering, and other illegal activities. It involves collecting and analyzing various documents and data to determine customers’ identity, financial position, and risk profile. *For more details:* KYC Hub. (13 April 2025). What is KYC (Know Your Customer)? KYC Hub. <https://www.kychub.com/blog/kyc-know-your-customer/>

⁷⁶ U.S. Department of the Treasury. (19 July, 2024). Treasury sanctions leader and primary member of the Cyber Army of Russia Reborn. Retrieved from <https://home.treasury.gov/news/press-releases/jy2473>

⁷⁷ Watts, C. (2 June, 2024). How Russia is trying to disrupt the 2024 Paris Olympic Games. Microsoft On the Issues. Retrieved from <https://blogs.microsoft.com/on-the-issues/2024/06/02/russia-cyber-bots-disinformation-2024-paris-olympics/>; - (ii) Cantos, M.,

Operational Relay Box⁷⁸, to obscure operator traffic to and from target environments; targeting network edge devices; exploiting zero day vulnerabilities). Pro-Chinese information operations (IO) are expected to continue targeting countries and regions considered as strategic priorities (in particular, Taiwan and the United States) through actions, such as voter impersonation, promotion of vote-rigging disinformation, and video content with artificial intelligence-generated news hosts;

(iii) Beyond the ongoing conflict between Israel, Hamas, Hezbollah and Houtis, Iranian malicious actors will continue to target governmental and telecommunications organizations in the Middle East and North Africa. According to the authors of the above mentioned Google Cloud Security's report, Iran long-standing objectives (regime stability, economic development, and regional influence) will not stop targeting dissidents, key individuals, and organizations involved in Iranian or regional politics, and technologies to enhance Iran's military capabilities, and technologies to enhance Iran's military capabilities;

(iv) North Korea will continue to seek strategic targets in South Korea and the United States, as well as the United Kingdom, Germany, Australia, China, and Russia. In terms of tactics used, the Google Cloud Security's report emphasizes open-source software packages trojanised in social engineering operations aimed at software developers. Likewise, North Korean malicious actors will continue to work on revenue generation through IT workers and cryptocurrency theft.

Russian Federation

53. On 5 September 2024, the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), the Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA), the National Security Agency (NSA), and a number of other international partners published a release pointing out that cyber actors affiliated with the Russian General Staff's Main Intelligence Directorate (the 161st Specialized Training Centre, Unit 29155) have been responsible for external espionage, sabotage, and reputational damage since at least 2020. The cyber actors of GRU Unit 29155 have been distributing the malware Whisper Gate against various Ukrainian organizations since 13 January 2022; these actors differ from other GRU-affiliated groups, such as Unit 26165 and Unit 74455⁷⁹.

& Collier, J. (5 June, 2024). Phishing for Gold: Cyber Threats Facing the 2024 Paris Olympics. Google Cloud Blog. Retrieved from <https://cloud.google.com/blog/topics/threat-intelligence/cyber-threats-2024-paris-olympics/>

; (iii) Cyber Threat Alliance. (9 July, 2024). CTA 2024 Olympics Threat Assessment Report. Retrieved from <https://www.cyberthreatalliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/CTA-2024-Olympics-Threat-Assessment-Report - Combined.pdf>

⁷⁸ S2 Research Team. (29 October, 2024). An Introduction to Operational Relay Box (ORB) Networks - Unpatched, Forgotten, and Obscured. Security Boulevard. Retrieved from <https://securityboulevard.com/2024/10/an-introduction-to-operational-relay-box-orb-networks-unpatched-forgotten-and-obscured/>

⁷⁹ Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency. (5 September, 2024). Russian Military Cyber Actors Target US and Global Critical Infrastructure. Retrieved from <https://www.cisa.gov/news-events/cybersecurity-advisories/aa24-249a>

54. Ransomware-as-a-service operation, Phobos has recently attacked hospitals in Romania and, according to US law enforcement, municipal and county governments, emergency services, education, public health, and other critical infrastructure, as the Record (18 November 2024) reported⁸⁰⁻⁸¹.
55. FBI and Australian law enforcement agencies have indicated that the BianLian ransomware actors are likely based in Russia and have multiple affiliates based in Russia. The FBI and the Australian Cyber Security Centre issued an updated alert⁸² on the group. BianLian has attracted attention for attacks on entities, such as Save The Children and health care companies, including the Boston Children's Health Physicians. In addition, the group claimed an attack on the Amherst burg Family Health Team, a Canadian health care company. Since January 2024, the group has focused on exfiltration-based extortion. Jonathan Greig (The Record, 21 November 2024) reported⁸³.
56. A hacktivist group probably based in India has been detected distributing ransomware against state and public entities in countries that oppose Russian interests. The group has been active since at least March 2024 and is known as CyberVolk: it uses current geopolitical issues to justify its attacks. In 2024, CyberVolk claimed to have compromised the networks of critical infrastructure and scientific institutions in Japan, France and the UK. A report by the cybersecurity firm Sentinel One⁸⁴ points out that CyberVolk has already claimed alliances with other pro-Russia hacktivist groups. The group is just one of many politically motivated threats highlighted after Russia's invasion of Ukraine in 2024. Daryna Antoniuk (The Record, 26 November 2024) reported⁸⁵.
57. European and British security and intelligence agencies are increasingly blaming the Russian Federation. Kestutis Budrys, Senior National Security Advisor to Lithuanian President Gitanas Nausėda, accused Russian intelligence services of conducting unconventional kinetic operations

⁸⁰ Warminsky, J. (18 November, 2024). Russian national in US custody in Phobos ransomware investigation. The Record. Retrieved from <https://therecord.media/russian-national-in-custody-extradited>

⁸¹ Warminsky, J. (21 November, 2024). Phobos ransomware indictment sheds light on long-running, quietly successful scheme. The Record. Retrieved from <https://therecord.media/phobos-ransomware-indictment-five-years-under-the-radar>

⁸² Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency. (20 November, 2024). #StopRansomware: BianLian Ransomware Group. Retrieved from <https://www.cisa.gov/news-events/cybersecurity-advisories/aa23-136a>

⁸³ Greig, J. (21 November, 2024). FBI says BianLian based in Russia, moving from ransomware attacks to extortion. The Record. Retrieved from <https://therecord.media/fbi-says-bianlian-based-in-russia-switching-tactics>

⁸⁴ Walter, J. (25 November, 2024). CyberVolk: A deep dive into the hacktivists, tools, and ransomware fueling pro-Russian cyber attacks. SentinelOne. Retrieved from <https://www.sentinelone.com/labs/cybervolk-a-deep-dive-into-the-hacktivists-tools-and-ransomware-fueling-pro-russian-cyber-attacks/>

⁸⁵ Antoniuk, D. (26 November, 2024). 'CyberVolk' hacktivists use ransomware in support of Russian interests. The Record. Retrieved from <https://therecord.media/cybervolk-india-hacktivists-russia-ransomware>

against NATO countries.⁸⁶ German intelligence chief Bruno Kahl stated⁸⁷ that Russian operational activity in Europe had reached an unprecedented level.

58. A new Laboratory for AI Security Research will come soon into operation to protect the UK and its allies from the malicious use of AI by hostile nations, such as Russia. It will collaborate with institutions from Five Eyes countries and NATO. The lab is necessary to ensure that London remains at the forefront of the new arms race with adversaries such as Russia and North Korea. Cyber warfare is now part of the daily threats to democratic countries, as James Coker (Info security Magazine, 25 November 2024)⁸⁸ reported.
59. In the context of the hybrid warfare waged by Moscow, it is important to highlight acts of sabotage that are not cyber-attacks: targeting critical infrastructure is part of Moscow's hybrid strategy.
60. The damage to two submarine cables in the Baltic Sea on 17-18 November 2024 is the latest case of suspected sabotage. V. Adm Didier Malaterre, the deputy commander of Nato's Allied Maritime Command (Marcom), said to The Guardian (16 April 2024) that the network of underwater cables and pipes on which Europe's power and communications depend were not built to withstand the 'hybrid warfare' being pursued by Moscow and other Nato adversaries⁸⁹⁻⁹⁰⁻⁹¹. Such sabotage is a hybrid warfare that intersects with cyber threats: submarine cables transmit most of the international data traffic, the destruction of which can affect access to the internet and disrupt cybersecurity systems. These activities have direct consequences for democratic resilience. Democracy, elections, media, and the discourse all depend on stable, secure communication networks. Attacks on such infrastructure can obstruct electoral processes, undermine access to reliable information, and affect trust by citizens in information and the deliberations it provides, the long-term goal being to destabilize democratic societies and cause harm internally.

⁸⁶ Sytas, A., & Shepardson, D. (6 November, 2024). Lithuania says Russia responsible for exploding parcels that caused fires. Reuters. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/lithuania-says-russia-responsible-exploding-parcels-that-caused-fires-2024-11-05/>

⁸⁷ Körömi, C., & von der Burchard, H. (14 October, 2024). German spy chief warns of Russian sabotage and potential attack on NATO. Politico. Retrieved from <https://www.politico.eu/article/germany-intelligence-spy-chief-warns-sabotages-russia-attack-nato-bruno-kahl-bnd/>

⁸⁸ Coker, J. (25 November, 2024). UK launches AI security lab to combat Russian cyber threats. Infosecurity Magazine. Retrieved from <https://www.infosecurity-magazine.com/news/uk-ai-security-lab-russia/>

⁸⁹ Borger, J. (March, 2024). Undersea hybrid warfare threatens security of 1bn, NATO commander warns. The Guardian. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2024/apr/16/undersea-hybrid-warfare-threatens-security-of-1bn-nato-commander-warns>

⁹⁰ Ondraskova, J., Berzina, K., & Arts, S. (26 November, 2024). Navigating Murky Waters. German Marshall Fund of the United States. Retrieved from <https://www.gmfus.org/news/navigating-murky-waters>

⁹¹ Höller, L. (9 December, 2024). The shallow Baltic Sea holds deep secrets about a hybrid war on NATO. Defense News. Retrieved from <https://www.defensenews.com/special-reports/2024/12/09/the-shallow-baltic-sea-holds-deep-secrets-about-a-hybrid-war-on-nato/>

61. Submarine cables are just one of the infrastructures under attack. In early 2024, the Swedish Security Service⁹² discovered that a Russian Orthodox church, located in Västerås (central Sweden) near an airport and other critical infrastructures, was linked to Russian intelligence operations. The airport is used for Swedish military operations and is close to an electricity and district heating supplier and a number of energy companies: these include the Westinghouse Electric Company, supplier of nuclear energy to Energoatom, the Ukrainian state-owned company that operates the country's four nuclear power plants.
62. As the illegal war in Ukraine continues, Russian sabotage operations are growing and, in some cases, even less secret. Recently, the Russian Federation reportedly targeted water supplies in Finland, Germany and Sweden⁹³. Other incidents include an arson attack on a company in east London linked to Ukraine, an attack on US military facilities in Bavaria⁹⁴, and a wave of disruption of GPS and automatic identification systems (AIS) in the Baltic Sea.

People's Republic of China

63. A report by France's Orange Cyberdefense, *The hidden network. How China unites state, corporate, and academic assets for cyber offensive campaigns*⁹⁵, analyses how, in China, hundreds of private cybersecurity companies, technology service providers, and universities are supporting the State apparatus to develop offensive cyber capabilities to support Chinese strategic (military, economic, and geopolitical) objectives. The authors of the report highlight how China's offensive capabilities are supported by a complex, multi-layered ecosystem. The report provides in-depth context on the success Chinese cyber actors have achieved by infiltrating critical US infrastructure (breaching government, military and corporate networks, stealing defence data, trade secrets and intellectual property) and beyond. The Chinese authorities promote formal and informal partnerships with technology companies: the military-civil fusion strategy requires companies to share their technological advances with the State. This creates a feedback loop in which innovations from the private sector directly improve the capabilities of the State. Concerns are growing in the US about Chinese cyber-attacks (among others, the Volt Typhoon operations that targeted critical infrastructure): in its 2024 annual report, the US Office of the Director of National Intelligence described China as the most active and persistent cyber threat to US government,

⁹² Duxbury, C. (11 November, 2024). New Russian church raises suspicions in Swedish town. Politico. Retrieved from <https://www.politico.eu/article/new-russian-orthodox-church-suspicion-sweden-town-vasteras/>

⁹³ Reuters. (21 October, 2024). Russia's suspected sabotage campaign steps up in Europe. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/world/russias-suspected-sabotage-campaign-steps-up-europe-2024-10-21/>

⁹⁴ Parker, J. (18 August, 2024). Trade reaction: BBC shines light on whisky cask scams. BBC News. Retrieved from <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/clyn8vk4g42o>

⁹⁵ Malachinski, P., & World Watch team. (22 October, 2024). *The hidden network: How China unites state, corporate, and academic assets for cyber offensive campaigns*. Orange Cyberdefense. Note: The analysis cut-off date for this report was October 22, 2024. Retrieved from <https://research.cert.orange cyberdefense.com/hidden-network/report.html>

private sector, and critical infrastructure networks. Orange's research found that the four main government actors responsible for building and executing China's cyber-offence capabilities are the People's Liberation Army (PLA), the Ministry of State Security (MSS), the Ministry of Public Security (MPS) and the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology (MIIT). Actively recruiting or supporting private hackers and hacktivists in activities such as data theft, website defacement and distributed denial-of-service attacks are their main activities.

64. A report by Sekoia (13 November 2024), A three-beat waltz: The ecosystem behind Chinese state-sponsored cyber threats⁹⁶, analyses the system set up by the country to carry out offensive operations. In addition to State actors, patriotic hacker communities are reported to be progressively integrated into State-sponsored operations. These hackers helped develop malicious payloads, used by the China-nexus Advanced Persistent Threats (APTS), such as Plug X and Shadow Pad. State actors subcontract cyber offensive services at provincial and city levels and increasingly outsource cyber offensive capabilities to private entities (both incumbent technology giants and smaller companies such as I-SOON): rather, China-nexus APTS are a mix of private and state actors cooperating in conducting offensive operations.
65. In March 2024, the New York General District Court indicted Chinese citizens for cyber-attacks against US officials and critical infrastructure⁹⁷. The case was linked to the Hubei provincial branch of China's Ministry of State Security, the country's main civilian intelligence and counterintelligence agency, which had set up front companies for hacker groups. Provincial governments and local intelligence agencies play an important but still little investigated role in China's cyber operations, as Joseph Christian Agbagala (Binding Hook, 5 November 2024) reported⁹⁸.
66. Salt Typhoon, a Chinese State-sponsored hacker group, has, according to some researchers, targeted telecommunications companies in South-East Asia with a new backdoor called GhostSpider. Salt Typhoon had already been targeted for undermining the networks of several telecommunications companies in the United States (Verizon, AT&T, Lumen Technologies, and T-Mobile). The cybersecurity company Trend Micro describes the operation in the report Game of

⁹⁶ Chavane, C., & Sekoia TDR. (13 November, 2024). A three beats waltz: The ecosystem behind Chinese state-sponsored cyber threats. Sekoia.io. Retrieved from <https://blog.sekoia.io/a-three-beats-waltz-the-ecosystem-behind-chinese-state-sponsored-cyber-threats/>

⁹⁷ Office of Public Affairs. (25 March, 2024). Seven hackers associated with Chinese government charged with computer intrusions targeting perceived critics of China and U.S. businesses and politicians. United States Department of Justice. <https://www.justice.gov/archives/opa/pr/seven-hackers-associated-chinese-government-charged-computer-intrusions-targeting-perceived>

⁹⁸ Agbagala, J. C. (5 November, 2024). Provincial governments play an underappreciated role in China's cyber operations. Binding Hook. <https://bindinghook.com/articles-hooked-on-trends/provincial-governments-play-an-underappreciated-role-in-chinas-cyber-operations/>

Emperor: Unveiling Long Term Earth Estries Cyber Intrusions⁹⁹. Earth Estries (the name it uses to refer to Salt Typhoon) is a well-organized group with a clear division of labour. Salt Typhoon has successfully hit over 20 organizations in various industries, including telecommunications, technology, consulting, chemicals, and transportation in the US, Asia Pacific, the Middle East, and South Africa since 2023. Trend Micro noted that Salt Typhoon may share tools with other Chinese State-sponsored hackers, as their techniques and malware often overlap.

North Korea

67. In an analysis for the think tank Observer Research Foundation (21 November 2024)¹⁰⁰, Abhishek Sharma writes that with the strengthened military-political partnership between North Korean and the Russian Federation, the North Korean regime is expected to invest more in military modernization, particularly in emerging domains, such as space and cyberspace: the latter is particularly important for sabotage, espionage, cyber theft, and intelligence gathering. A crescendo of cyber-attacks against South Korea, the US, and Japan is likely to occur.
68. In order to increase its conventional capabilities, the North Korean regime has strengthened its asymmetric forces and cyber-hacking infrastructure. South Korea's National Intelligence Service (NIS) reported that, as of 2024, North Korea has 8,400 cyber-crime personnel, a significant increase from the previous year. The NIS also reported 1.62 million hacking attempts in 2023, a 36% increase from 2022.
69. North Korea is one of the most heavily sanctioned States by the UN Security Council and has deployed circumvention strategies. For example, between 2017 and 2023 (Note by the President of the Security Council, 7 Marzo 2024)¹⁰¹, \$3 million in cryptocurrencies were found to have been stolen to numerous organizations in various countries around the world (for details see annex 95 of the Note by the President of the Security Council mentioned above). Now, IT workers are added to the apparatus of subjects working to support the regime: operating in China, Russia, South-East Asia and Africa, they use freelance work platforms posing as foreign nationals¹⁰². Chandana Seshadri (Binding Hook, 19 November 2024)¹⁰³ informs about the technologies and tactics used

⁹⁹ Chang, L. M., Chen, T., Bermejo, L., & Lee, T. (25 November, 2024). Game of Emperor: Unveiling long term Earth Estries cyber intrusions. Trend Micro. https://www.trendmicro.com/en_us/research/24/k/earth-estries.html

¹⁰⁰ Sharma, A. (21 November, 2024). North Korea's cyber strategy: An initial analysis. Observer Research Foundation. <https://www.orfonline.org/research/north-korea-s-cyber-strategy-an-initial-analysis>

¹⁰¹ United Nations. (7 March, 2024). Report on the impact of cyber operations on international security. <https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/n24/032/68/pdf/n2403268.pdf>

¹⁰² Schappert, S. (22 November, 2024). North Korean IT worker scams lead to FBI seizure of fake domains, expose new tactics. Cybernews. <https://cybernews.com/security/north-korea-it-worker-scam-fbi-seizes-domains-tactics-microsoft/>

¹⁰³ Seshadri, C. (19 November, 2024). Freelance cyber networks fuel North Korean nuclear ambitions. Binding Hook. <https://bindinghook.com/articles-hooked-on-trends/freelance-cyber-networks-fuel-north-korean-nuclear-ambitions/>

and draws attention to the security risks for foreign countries: the KnowBe4 incident¹⁰⁴ is interesting and illustrative. The security company Nisos has noted the evolution of this campaign of false North Korean IT workers, believing that more and more are trying to earn money to finance Pyongyang's ballistic missile and nuclear weapons development programs.¹⁰⁵

Islamic Republic of Iran

70. Nitsan Yasser and Danny Citrinowicz (INSS, 12 November 2024) describe seven foreign influence groups, active in Israel from October 2023 to May 2024, and traceable to foreign State entities, particularly Iranian. In many cases, social media platforms have become 'mediators' in information warfare: it is on such platforms that hostile agents can spread malicious content and false information. Such platforms have become one of the arenas in which the digital dimension of warfare takes place: (i) Aryeh Yehuda News Flashes (to spread propaganda and false information by posing as a local news update channel, groups were opened on WhatsApp, Telegram and Facebook, presenting themselves as an extreme right-wing Israeli group); (ii) Egrof (presenting itself as a far-right Kahanist group), the platforms TikTok, Instagram, Twitter, Facebook and WhatsApp were used; the aim was to spread divisions and tensions in Israeli society, exacerbate friction between Jews and Arabs, and incite against the Israeli Security Forces); (iii) Dema'ot HaMilhama (database of people murdered, killed or taken hostage, promoting content to exacerbate tensions and encourage radicalization; the group also disseminated deceptive recruitment tactics, specifically targeting Israelis); (iv) BringHomeNow (with the aim of establishing a local presence and collecting personal data from Israelis, the operation used names and hashtags similar to those used by the Hostage Family Forum, using Telegram and engaging in authentic online activities); (v) Ḥasrot onim (the operation tried to insert itself into the local discourse by spreading messages aimed at demoralizing Israeli women, including female soldiers, injured or killed women, and women hostages, by calling them 'helpless'); (vi) Kan+ (an operation that used digital assets to promote a fake platform for conducting research and surveys, exploiting some of the visual elements associated with the Kan 11 TV channel; the objective was to gather information on Israelis who responded to surveys); (vii) Second Israel (the operation, for over two years, focused on various issues in Israeli public discourse)¹⁰⁶.

¹⁰⁴ Sjouwerman, S. (23 July, 2024). How a North Korean fake IT worker tried to infiltrate us.

KnowBe4. <https://blog.knowbe4.com/how-a-north-korean-fake-it-worker-tried-to-infiltrate-us>

¹⁰⁵ Beek, K. (4 March, 2025). North Korea's latest 'IT worker' scheme seeks nuclear funds. Dark Reading. <https://www.darkreading.com/remote-workforce/north-korea-it-worker-scheme-nuclear-funds>

¹⁰⁶ Yasur, N., & Citrinowicz, D. (12 November, 2024). Iranian foreign information manipulation and interference during the Swords of Iron War. Institute for National Security Studies. <https://www.inss.org.il/publication/iran-influence/>

71. The Israeli cybersecurity firm Check Point (14 November 2024)¹⁰⁷ has detected a new remote access and information-stealing Trojan used by actors linked to Iran. WezRat is the code name assigned to the malware believed to be the work of Cotton Sandstorm, an Iranian hacker group better known by the cover names Emennet Pasargad and, more recently, Aria Sepehr Ayandehsazan (ASA). According to Check Point, WezRat was distributed to several Israeli entities as part of phishing emails depicting the Israeli National Cyber Directorate (INCD). Emennet Pasargad’s targets are entities in the United States, Europe, and the Middle East: the group poses a threat to both direct political opponents and anyone with influence over Iran’s domestic or international narrative.

Case Studies

72. 2024 has been a particularly important year to observe democratic systems under conditioning and attack. The year 2025 is also expected to be problematic and fraught with risk for the Western democracies: in the context of the hybrid warfare waged by Moscow, it is very important to emphasize Polish Prime Minister Donald Tusk’s very recent appeal about the risk of possible terrorist attacks, to destabilize Poland and Europe, that can be traced back to the Russian Federation¹⁰⁸. Besides the elections for the European Parliament, the President of the United States of America, among others, a particularly important case study concerns Romania.

Figure 5: Strains on Eastern European Democracies¹⁰⁹

¹⁰⁷ Check Point Team. (14 November, 2024). Spotlight on Iranian cyber group Emennet Pasargad’s malware. Check Point. <https://blog.checkpoint.com/research/spotlight-on-iranian-cyber-group-emennet-pasargads-malware/>

¹⁰⁸ Gera, V. (15 January, 2025). Poland's leader accuses Russia of planning acts of sabotage against airlines worldwide. Associated Press. <https://apnews.com/article/poland-russia-airlines-tusk-27ee21c74b10bf1874deaed572229c96>

¹⁰⁹ This infographic has been created by the PAM research team, illustrating the strains on Eastern European democracies.

73. Speaking of Romania, and citing the recent cases of Moldova and Georgia, former US Secretary of State Anthony Blinken said (OSCE Ministerial Council, Valletta, 5 December 2024): This year, the OSCE observed more than a dozen elections - including the recent United States election - delivering assessments that remain the gold standard for free and fair contests. In Moldova, the OSCE affirmed a well-administered runoff despite Russian interference, and now Romanian authorities are uncovering a Russian effort - large in scale and well-funded - to influence the recent presidential election, contrary to OSCE standards. Meanwhile in Georgia, observers shed light on troubling reports of voter intimidation and efforts by the ruling party to tilt the playing field in its favor¹¹⁰.
74. The elections held last 24 November were annulled by the Constitutional Court that cited the Article 50(3) of the Romanian electoral law (which allows for annulment if fraud or significant interference can affect the outcome of the elections). The far right and unknown candidate Călin Georgescu obtained 22.9%, followed by the pro-EU candidate of Save Romania Union Elena Lasconi (19.18%), and the current Prime Minister Marcel Ciolacu (19.15%) of the Social Democratic Party. The cancellation of the elections was triggered by a meeting of the Supreme National Defence Council and the declassification of secret files¹¹¹. The victory of Călin Georgescu, populist and pro-Russian, is under scrutiny following possible interference in the election campaign by Moscow.¹¹² Georgescu's election campaign, as pointed out by Alexandru Damian (London School of Economics and Political Science, 13 December 2024)¹¹³ was characterized by extreme right-wing rhetoric and disinformation, focusing on the most fragile part of the population and the diaspora: Georgescu insisted on alternative medicine, anti-vaccine sentiments, Romania's exit from the EU, opposition to support for Ukraine and nationalist propaganda. Georgescu was not a popular politician in the country: his claim in the first round of the presidential election was decisively accelerated in the last two weeks before the vote, when

¹¹⁰ Blinken, A. J. (5 December, 2024). Plenary statement at the 31st OSCE Ministerial Council, Valletta, Malta. United States Mission to the OSCE.

<https://osce.usmission.gov/plenary-statement-31st-osce-ministerial-council-valletta-malta-december-5-2024/>

¹¹¹ Pantazi, C. (4 December, 2024). President Iohannis declassified information from secret services about Călin Georgescu: TikTok account activities were coordinated by a state actor. G4Media. <https://www.g4media.ro/breaking-presedintele-iohannis-a-declasificat-informatiile-de-la-serviciile-secrete-despre-calin-georgescu-activitatea-conturilor-de-tiktok-ar-fi-fost-coordonata-de-un-actor-statal-tipar-de-campani.html>

¹¹² Euronews. (6 December, 2024). Romanian Constitutional Court blocks presidential run-off. <https://www.euronews.com/my-europe/2024/12/06/romanian-constitutional-court-blocks-presidential-run-off>

¹¹³ Damian, A. (13 December, 2024). The annulment of Romania's presidential election reflects both foreign meddling and domestic failures. EUROPP Blog. <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/europpblog/2024/12/13/the-annulment-of-romania-presidential-election-reflects-both-foreign-meddling-and-domestic-failures/>

some 25,000 suspicious accounts came into play on Tik Tok¹¹⁴, Meta¹¹⁵, and Telegram¹¹⁶. On 18 May 2025, in the second round of presidential elections, pro-European candidate Nicușor Dan won, defeating far-right leader George Simion. Despite intense political polarization, online disinformation campaigns and attempts at interference, Romania demonstrated its democratic resilience. Dan won in urban centers and secured the votes of minorities and Moldovan voters, while Simion won in rural areas and among the diaspora in Western Europe.

75. Russia's strategic objective of undermining the West is closely linked to its goal of fragmenting the European Union and NATO. In this context, Romania plays a particularly important role. Antonia Colibășanu (Foreign Policy Research Institute, 11 December 2024)¹¹⁷ describes some of the main reasons. Romania occupies a strategic position to defend NATO's eastern flank and hosts important military infrastructure of the Alliance. The country is committed to reducing its energy dependence from Moscow (through the Neptun Deep project for indigenous natural gas production, which would make Romania an important energy producer and potential exporter within the European Union). Over the past two decades, Russia has consistently operated in terms of influencing the local population, calling out the importance for Romanians to keep natural resources in their own hands and criticizing American investments in oil and gas. The Russian Federation has also supported campaigns insisting on Romania's Christian nationalist sentiment, although the Romanian Orthodox Church is officially linked to Constantinople, Russia aims to push for divisions between Romania and its Western allies. Disinformation campaigns by Russia began in the early 2000s, with a substantial increase in Romania since 2016: many of the propaganda messages, promoting official Russian positions, appeared in Romanian on social media and originated from Moldova (where both Romanian and Russian are spoken). A particularly sensitive topic that was used by the Russian Federation in disinformation campaigns in Romania concerned support for Ukraine: Russia falsely claimed that Ukrainian refugee children receive higher allocations from the State than Romanian ones.
76. Although Russia has been active in Romania for many years, it intensified its propaganda in the country during the latest presidential elections. The theme ties in with Russian war of aggression against Ukraine. Russia strategically wants to bring southern Ukraine, including Odesa, under its

¹¹⁴ Expert Forum. (23 November, 2024). Extremism and momentum: How Călin Georgescu has risen in the polls. <https://expertforum.ro/en/extremism-and-momentum-how-calin-georgescu-has-risen-in-the-polls/>

¹¹⁵ K. Guillaume. (9 December, 2024). Meta's role in Romania's 2024 presidential election.

CheckFirst. <https://checkfirst.network/research-note-metas-role-in-romaniyas-2024-presidential-election/>

¹¹⁶ Vrabie, M. (8 December, 2024). KOMANDA KREMLIN: The Russian machinery behind Călin Georgescu. Public Record. <https://publicrecord.ro/2024/12/08/komanda-kremlin-masinaria-rusa-din-spatele-lui-calin-georgescu/>

¹¹⁷ Colibasanu, A. (11 December, 2024). Romania's electoral crisis: A blueprint for defending democracy. Foreign Policy Research Institute. <https://www.fpri.org/article/2024/12/romaniyas-electoral-crisis-a-blueprint-for-defending-democracy/>

occupation before any negotiating table is opened. To achieve this goal, which would deprive Kiev of access to the Black Sea and thus the possibility of trading with the rest of the world, a military campaign would not guarantee results in the short term: tactically, Russia would have to make it very difficult or impossible for Ukraine to export goods through the Black Sea. In this context, Romania becomes essential: the country has been very important in strategically supporting Ukraine, not only militarily.

77. While geopolitical reasons are important, in the medium to long term it will be essential to build social resilience and strengthen Romania's democracy¹¹⁸. The real danger of Russia's strategy lies in its ability to exploit the vulnerabilities present in Romanian society (e.g. uneven economic growth, polarization, disparities between urban and non-urban areas) by promoting narratives that meet and feed social unease and the population's distrust in the country's institutions.
78. The situation in Georgia is another interesting case study. A decisive step in recent months was the entry into force (August 2024) of the law on 'foreign agents'¹¹⁹. In the October 2024 parliamentary elections, amidst much tension, the Georgian Dream party won 54% of the vote: there were numerous violations (pressure on voters, vote buying and misuse of public resources), reported - among others - by the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe¹²⁰. The President, Salome Zourabichvili, spoke of Russian interference in the country¹²¹.
79. Prior to the parliamentary elections, State media disseminated narratives¹²² to discredit pro-Western politicians, while at the same time fueling skepticism towards the EU and NATO. Cybersecurity experts analyzed attempts¹²³ to breach Georgian election infrastructure, generating doubts about the integrity of the voting process. The use of financial resources by Russia to bribe¹²⁴ political and business personalities was also reported. All this, besides undermining the country's democratic institutions, has tilted the balance for the Georgian Dream party.

¹¹⁸ Popescu-Zamfir, O. (10 December, 2024). Romania's election crisis: A stark warning for NATO nations on Russian meddling. European Council on Foreign Relations. <https://ecfr.eu/article/romania-election-crisis-a-stark-warning-for-nato-nations-on-russian-meddling/>

¹¹⁹ Kucera, J. (24 August, 2024). Defying controversial 'foreign-agent' law, Georgian NGOs are ready to fight. Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty. <https://www.rferl.org/a/georgia-ngos-foreign-agent-law/33090157.html>

¹²⁰ Gavin, G., & Parulava, D. (27 October, 2024). Georgia elections marred by intimidation and interference, observers warn. Politico. <https://www.politico.eu/article/georgia-elections-marred-by-intimidation-and-interference-observers-warn/>

¹²¹ Associated Press. (28 October, 2024). Georgia's president accuses Russia of election meddling, urges the West to back protests. <https://apnews.com/article/georgia-russia-election-european-union-8f040cb30e1d9c9e778383cbcb7b2c1>

¹²² Echols, W. (31 October, 2024). Accused of interference in Georgia, Russia pumps up anti-US propaganda. Voice of America. <https://www.voanews.com/a/accused-of-interference-in-georgia-russia-pumps-up-anti-us-propaganda-/7846721.html>

¹²³ Nardelli, A., & Gallagher, R. (22 October, 2024). How Russia's spies hacked the entire nation of Georgia. The Economic Times. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/international/world-news/how-russias-spies-hacked-the-entire-nation-of-georgia/articleshow/114454477.cms?from=mdr>

¹²⁴ Transparency International Georgia. (31 March, 2025). Alleged cases of high-level corruption A periodically updated list. Retrieved from <https://transparency.ge/en/blog/alleged-cases-high-level-corruption-periodically-updated-list>

80. The strategic questions concern the future of the country. The Georgian Dream party has 89 seats in parliament. The situation in Georgia is very tense, and new attacks on civil society are likely, the introduction of authoritarian laws and the rise of anti-Western rhetoric, as has been the case over the past year¹²⁵.
81. Using Georgia as an examining case study that happened in August 2024, the implementation of the law of foreign agents has oppressed activities of the civil society organizations to the extreme. NGOs were once financed by Western funding, but most are currently facing the choice of keeping foreign financial association to a minimum or failing to have any legal impact on them. Although they were rejected at first by some of the organizations, the long-term impact of this pressure is likely to increase resistance in the long run and may be a potential backlash to democracy and reduced civic space.¹²⁶
82. Again, in Georgia, the recent history of the country is a straightforward illustration of how institutional choices can lead to decisions that are against popular democratic visions. The fact that the country is threatened with the withdrawal of accession negotiations by the EU and sanctions against its national leadership makes Georgia at risk of integrating into the Western establishments. Although the view of the citizens towards joining NATO was highly in favor (65%), with almost 80 percent voting on the EU membership during a late 2023 public opinion survey, the gap between their expectations and the country they live in was brought into question via the results showing the majority of the legislature, irrespective of governmental support, was against the accession of both organizations.
83. Moldova's election results keep it on a pro-Western course. But it is a fragile democracy. The country is still struggling with ethnic and regional tensions: Russia is exploiting these weaknesses. Russian actions are part of a pattern: Russia has long acted in the country, and in the post-Soviet space, to maximize its influence and delegitimize the influence of the West. Maria Sandu, the pro-Western president of Moldova, won¹²⁷ re-election on 3 November 2024 against Alexandr Stoianoglo, the man she denounced as 'Moscow's man'. On 20 October 2024, President Sandu also pushed for the organization of a referendum to include the 'irreversibility' of the country's

¹²⁵ Fraser, C., & Seskuria, N. (27 June, 2024). Georgia at a crossroads: Can the West still compete? Retrieved from <https://www.rusi.org/explore-our-research/publications/commentary/georgia-crossroads-can-west-still-compete>

¹²⁶ Euronews. (10 September, 2024). Majority of NGOs in Georgia refuse to register as foreign agents under new law. Retrieved from <https://www.euronews.com/2024/09/10/majority-of-ngos-in-georgia-refuse-to-register-as-foreign-agents-under-new-law>

¹²⁷ Higgins, A. (03 November, 2024). Sandu, pro-West Moldova president, wins re-election amid Russian interference claims. Retrieved from <https://www.nytimes.com/2024/11/03/world/europe/sandu-pro-west-moldova-president.html>

‘European path’ in Moldova’s constitution. The referendum passed, but by a tiny margin¹²⁸. Widespread irregularities were noted by observers.

84. The Moldovan election campaign was marked by significant Russian interference (cyber-attacks, spying at diaspora polling stations, vote buying). Alexandr Stoianoglo ran a campaign financed by the fugitive pro-Russian oligarch Ilan Shor and, ultimately, by the Kremlin. Although the Russians’ disruptive efforts had some effect, they were not decisive: the referendum passed by a much smaller margin than the polls had predicted only a few days earlier, apparently due to Russia’s success in illegally wooing undecided voters. In both the referendum and the presidential elections, the votes of the Moldovan diaspora determined the outcome.
85. In Moldova, Russia is using tools (disinformation, economic manipulation, cyber-attacks) to try to dominate Moldova’s security and foreign policies by exploiting its vulnerabilities. Russia’s hybrid warfare capabilities are enhanced because pro-Russian leaders in Moldova benefit¹²⁹ politically from the implicit threat of direct military aggression by Russia.
86. Russia’s methods in Moldova have varied according to local circumstances and opportunities and are not new. In late 2022, Russia used its near monopoly on natural gas to raise prices, causing an economic crisis. It then moved to more direct measures: financing pro-Russian political parties and public protests, saturating the local media environment with propaganda, and, according to some reports, plotting to replace the Sandu government. Moldova has key vulnerabilities that are ripe for exploitation by Russia: disapproval of Sandu’s pro-Western policies remains particularly strong in the countryside and among the older generations; about half of the population favors closer relations with Russia; Moldovan society is increasingly polarized, poverty is widespread, institutions are weak, and corruption is rampant. In recent months, the autonomous region of Gagauzian, populated by a Turkish-speaking ethnic group and where there are long-standing tensions with the central government, has become the object of Russian attention: the region’s leader, Evghenia Guțul, has close ties with Moscow and the pro-Russian oligarch Shor (tried in absentia for large-scale fraud and money laundering and sanctioned in 2022 by the United States for his role in fomenting political unrest).
87. Russia’s tight control over the separatist region of Transnistria remains a source of instability. It is a strategically important strip of land that hosts around 1,200 Russian troops and local militias. In recent months, relations with Moldova have become less tense. The region’s local economy has

¹²⁸ Rainsford, S. (21 October 2024). Moldova says “Yes” to pro-EU constitutional changes by tiny margin. Retrieved from <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c1wnr5qdx7o>

¹²⁹ Gasparyan, D., & Harward, C. (27 October, 2024). Possible Russian gains in Georgia and Moldova. Retrieved from <https://www.understandingwar.org/backgrounder/possible-russian-gains-georgia-and-moldova>

improved since Ukraine closed its border, a decision that has made Transnistria more dependent on trade with the European Union and less interested in breaking ties with the central government. Moldova has also strengthened its resilience in other areas: for example, since December 2022, the country has become less dependent on natural Gas supply from Russia.

88. In the presidential elections held on 28 September 2025, Moldova had a choice between pro-EU and pro-Russia parties. The pro-EU Action and Solidarity Party won 50.2% of the vote, while the pro-Russia Patriotic Bloc came second with 24.18%. President Maia Sandu accused Russia of ‘massive interference’ after casting her vote. Her rival, Igor Dodon, claimed that the interference came from the West. Two pro-Russian parties were disqualified before the vote.^{130 131}
89. Among Western democracies, France is a particularly interesting case study with regard to disinformation that can be traced back to Moscow. On 14 February 2024, members of the editorial staff of France 24 were alerted: a deepfake video¹³² by journalist Julien Fanciulli had been circulating on Russian-language Telegram channels for several hours. On screen, the journalist is seen stating that Emmanuel Macron had cancelled a visit to Ukraine after the French secret service discovered that there was a risk of an assassination attempt against the President. This fake, also promoted by accounts on X, remains online and confined to pro-Russian disinformation spheres. But the question arises as to its ability to damage the channel's image.
90. The deepfake described in the previous point was followed by dozens of other pro-Russian poisonings, which repeatedly targeted France 24. In an international context punctuated by European and American elections and the Paris Olympics, disinformation specialists warned that digital interference campaigns would intensify in 2024. In 2024, the organization Check First documented several Russian digital interference operations, including Overload¹³³. Also known as Matriochka¹³⁴, this is a campaign that aims to discredit and saturate fact-checking networks: fake videos imitating Western media are first spread online, then broadcast on social networks or via e-mail through fake accounts, which directly contact the media to request verification, with the aim

¹³⁰ Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe. (04 July 2023). *Trends and risks in the use of cryptocurrency for terrorist financing*. https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/4/7/597800_0.pdf

¹³¹ Kottasová, I. (29 September 2025). *Moldova's election tests its EU ambitions amid Russian pressure*. CNN. <https://edition.cnn.com/2025/09/29/europe/moldova-election-eu-russia-intl-hnk>

¹³² Saint-Léger, A. (16 February, 2024). France 24 victime d'un deepfake: L'intox continue à circuler sur le web. Retrieved from <https://www.france24.com/fr/%C3%A9missions/info-ou-intox/20240216-france-24-victime-d-un-deepfake-l-intox-continue-%C3%A0-circuler-sur-le-web>

¹³³ Kremer, G. (12 September, 2024). Operation Overload: A growing disinformation threat now targeting the U.S. presidential election. Retrieved from <https://checkfirst.network/operation-overload-a-growing-disinformation-threat-now-targeting-the-u-s-presidential-election/>

¹³⁴ France 24. (27 January, 2024). Matriochka: The new anti-Ukrainian disinformation campaign targeting Western media. Retrieved from <https://www.france24.com/fr/info-en-continu/20240127-matriochka-la-nouvelle-campagne-de-d%C3%A9sinformation-anti-ukrainienne-%C3%A0-destination-des-m%C3%A9dias-occidentaux>

of saturating their activity. In March 2024, to give other examples, a fake front page of the magazine L'Hémicycle¹³⁵, with a caricature of Emmanuel Macron, was included in a deceptive montage of a France 24 broadcast. The manipulation was then disseminated by France 24, which used the identity of the newspaper. Again, the manipulation found space on the digital portal Pravda, a key player in the Portal Kombat operation as documented by Viginum¹³⁶, the service responsible for combating foreign digital interference.

91. An important question concerns the real impact of interference operations on public debate. In June 2024, the Viginum agency¹³⁷ emphasized the low level of engagement with publications resulting from Operation Matriochka. So did the cybersecurity company Recorded Future¹³⁸, which in a report published in June 2024 noted the negligible impact of Russian disinformation operations against the European and then French parliamentary elections. Russian interest is to see populist currents, more favorable to its strategic interests, in power in Europe and it is working to this end with these operations.
92. An important issue concerns future and new forms of interference, which will increasingly involve local influencers disseminating pro-Russian content, often for a fee. This is a 'grey zone', halfway between foreign interference (FIMI, Foreign Information Manipulation and Interference) and interference by local actors (DIMI, Domestic Information Manipulation and Interference) that is more difficult to detect. In December 2024, a Russian interference operation was revealed¹³⁹ that targeted more than 2,000 influencers in Europe, including several French influencers. Such interference, as happened in South-Saharan Africa, works when malicious actors are able to interact with local actors and vice versa: these are hybrid campaigns that trace the contours of disinformation that is more deeply rooted in local social realities and require renewed vigilance in the year 2025.

¹³⁵ Gallo, N. (22 March, 2024). Fake front page caricaturing Macron: A doctored France 24 excerpt broadcast by pro-Russian channels. Retrieved from <https://observers.france24.com/fr/europe/20240322-fausse-une-caricaturant-macron-un-extrait-retouch%C3%A9-de-france-24-diffus%C3%A9-par-des-canaux-pro-russes>

¹³⁶ Gasparyan, D., & Harward, C. (12 February, 2024). Portal Kombat: A structured and coordinated pro-Russian propaganda network. Retrieved from https://www.sgdsn.gouv.fr/files/files/20240212_NP_SGDSN_VIGINUM_RAPPORT-RESEAU-PORTAL-KOMBAT_VF.pdf

¹³⁷ Gallo, N. (10 June, 2024). Operation Matriochka: The pro-Russian campaign against the fact-checking community intensifies. Retrieved from <https://observers.france24.com/fr/europe/20240610-op%C3%A9ration-matriochka-la-campagne-prorusse-contre-la-communaut%C3%A9-des-fact-checkeurs-s-intensifie>

¹³⁸ Insikt Group. (28 June, 2024). Russian and Iranian influence networks target French elections. Retrieved from <https://www.recordedfuture.com/research/russian-and-iranian-influence-networks-target-french-elections>

¹³⁹ Le Monde. (18 December, 2024). War in Ukraine: Thousands of influencers, including French, approached to spread pro-Russian propaganda. Retrieved from https://www.lemonde.fr/pixels/article/2024/12/18/guerre-en-ukraine-des-milliers-d-influenceurs-dont-des-francais-approches-pour-diffuser-de-la-propagande-prorusse_6455494_4408996.html

93. Germany is also attacked by disinformation. This is a very particular case because Germany, especially with reference to the elections of 23 February, is at the center of a double threat: both from Russia and from Elon Musk. Various kinds of scandals have been invented using artificial intelligence and platforms such as X, Facebook, Telegram, and Bluesky. According to analysts, the aim is to support the far-right Alternative for Germany (AfD) both to destabilize European democracies and to criticize support for the Ukrainian cause.¹⁴⁰ According to a German government report, viewed by POLITICO¹⁴¹, Russian disinformation can be traced back to Operation Doppelganger, supported by the Kremlin, as claimed by the German Foreign Office.
94. A study by the Institute for Strategic Dialogue¹⁴² found that a bot network (over 6,000 accounts) amplifies the videos, even tagging news organizations or fact-checkers in their posts. Although the network is focusing on the German elections, none of the videos or posts are in German; this could mean that the network intends to overwhelm fact-checkers and mislead international observers rather than influence the Germans themselves.
95. In January 2025, Elon Musk interviewed Alice Weidel, AfD's candidate for chancellor, on his social network X. Jan Rathje of the Center for Monitoring, Analysis, and Strategy (CEMAS) pointed out that Musk was connected to numerous far-right accounts. DW Fast Check took an in-depth look at two of Musk's statements regarding the German federal elections.^{143 144}

Recommendations for MPs and Public Officials

96. Considering the previous evidence and analysis that have been stated across this report, the table below provides a systematic reflection of some of the major political and technical strategies that parliamentarians and other people in authority can implement to increase democratic resilience. The aim of these recommendations is to focus on a thorough response to disinformation and cyberattacks based on best practices and expert evaluations in shaping policy and legislative efforts in the future.

¹⁴⁰ DNYUZ. (13 February, 2025). Between Russia and Elon Musk, German voters face a dual front of disinformation. Retrieved from <https://dnyuz.com/2025/02/13/between-russia-and-elon-musk-german-voters-face-a-dual-front-of-disinformation/>

¹⁴¹ Lunday, C. (06 February, 2025). Putin's bot army tries to swing German election. Retrieved from <https://www.politico.eu/article/germany-election-flood-social-media-x-russia-bots-kremlin-operation-false-news/>

¹⁴² Institute for Strategic Dialogue. (13 February, 2025). Coordinated disinformation network uses AI, media impersonation to target German election. Retrieved from https://www.isdglobal.org/digital_dispatches/coordinated-disinformation-network-uses-ai-media-impersonation-to-target-german-election/

¹⁴³ Weber, J. (21 February, 2025). Fact check: No, the AfD did not win in fictional German youth elections. Retrieved from <https://www.dw.com/en/fact-check-no-the-afd-did-not-win-in-fictional-german-youth-elections/a-71701349>

¹⁴⁴ de Graaf, A. (21 February, 2025). Fact check: How Elon Musk is meddling in German elections. Retrieved from <https://www.dw.com/en/fact-check-how-elon-musk-is-meddling-in-german-elections/a-71676473>

Table 1: Strategic Responses to Disinformation and Cyberattacks: Political and Technical Perspectives.

Disinformation	Cyberattack
<i>Political Perspective</i>	<i>Political Perspective</i>
Strengthen democratic institutions to help it cope with disinformation initiatives.	Enhance public awareness and education on the impact of cyberattacks.
Promote transparency and accountability in governance.	Develop and implement advanced cybersecurity measures.
Foster international cooperation to combat disinformation.	Invest in research and development of technologies to detect and counter cyberattacks.
Enhance public awareness and education on the impact of disinformation.	Cyberattacks target critical infrastructure and democratic processes.
Implement policies to counter the spread of disinformation.	Integrate cybersecurity measures into national security strategies.
Address the role of social media in spreading disinformation.	Foster international cooperation to combat cyber threats.
<i>Technical Perspective</i>	<i>Technical Perspective</i>
Use AI and machine learning to detect and counter disinformation.	Use AI and machine learning to detect and counter cyberattacks.
Develop technologies to enhance information integrity.	Implement blockchain and other technologies to ensure information integrity.
Promote responsible design and development of AI technologies.	Develop innovative industrial strategies to bridge the gap between strategic goals and technological resources.
Ensure equitable development of AI to overcome biases.	Enhance cybersecurity through continuous monitoring and threat intelligence sharing.
Invest in cybersecurity infrastructure and training.	Invest in cybersecurity infrastructure and training.

Conclusion

97. Democracy is a complex process and, as such, characterized by constant emergencies. The concept of resilience touches all dimensions of the democratic experience of which electoral processes are a central and decisive element, but not the only one. Democracies need, first and foremost, a healthy information environment that enables citizens to participate in collective life and contribute to decisions. Elections, a fundamental moment of verification of the political ruling classes, must take place in appropriate contexts. However, the democratic ecosystem, primarily the information one, is ‘polluted’ by the actions of malevolent actors.
98. In a strategic analysis dated 7 October 2025, the European Union Institute for Security Studies (EUISS)¹⁴⁵ highlighted how Russia uses psychological operations to distort perceptions and manipulate behavior: a cognitive security approach is proposed to address these vulnerabilities. Malicious actors can erode trust and resilience and jeopardize transnational security.
99. Society exists in the midst of geopolitics of (in)security and, at the same time, within the framework of an ‘onlife’ condition where the physical and digital dimensions of reality are inseparable. The technological revolution appears unstoppable, and the governance of this phenomenon calls for the responsible involvement of all actors at national, regional and global levels. In line with the strategic perspectives expressed in United Nations documents and resolutions, as well as in major international fora, shares the urgency of working together to identify appropriate governance strategies and best practices. Has established a Permanent Parliamentary Observatory on AI and Emerging Technologies¹⁴⁶ and publishes a Daily and Weekly Digest on AI and Emerging Technologies¹⁴⁷. On 20 February 2025, during the 19th Plenary Session of PAM, H.E Sergio Mattarella, President of the Italian Republic, has been awarded the PAM Award as Champion of Peace and Democracy for his steadfast dedication to upholding democracy and freedom¹⁴⁸: President Mattarella has, on numerous occasions, emphasized the importance of working together for a governance of the Internet and new technologies aimed at the common good and the strengthening of democratic systems for the protection of rights and freedoms and to prevent and counter foreign interferences and disinformation. On 10 October 2025, in Tallinn (Estonia), during the 20th meeting of the Heads of State of the Arraiolos Group, President Mattarella highlighted the

¹⁴⁵ Beatrice Catena. (7 October 2025). Smoke and Mirrors: Building EU Resilience against Manipulation through Cognitive Security. European Union Institute for Security Studies (EUISS). <https://www.iss.europa.eu/publications/briefs/smoke-and-mirrors-building-eu-resilience-against-manipulation-through-cognitive>

¹⁴⁶ Parliamentary Assembly of the Mediterranean – Center for Global Studies. (18, November 2024). The malicious use of AI and emerging technologies by terrorist and criminal groups: Impact on security, legislation, and governance. <https://www.cgspam.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/PAM-CGS-Report-on-AI-and-Emerging-Technologies-1.pdf>

¹⁴⁷ Parliamentary Assembly of the Mediterranean. (2025). Daily digest on AI and emerging technologies. <https://pam.int/digest-on-ai-and-emerging-technologies/>

¹⁴⁸ Parliamentary Assembly of the Mediterranean. (20 February, 2025). PAM Awards 2025. Retrieved from <https://pam.int/pam-awards-2025/>

unknowns associated with artificial intelligence, the close link between technology and security, and the use of AI to spread disinformation and influence public opinion: fake news is a highly relevant issue.

100. In a climate of hate speech, political, and social polarization threats to the integrity of democratic systems are, first and foremost, threats to the protection and guarantee of the fundamental rights and freedoms of every person and every human community: all the stakeholders must be involved. During the first Council of Europe Forum on Business and Human Rights (BRAVE 2025)¹⁴⁹, held on 21 October 2025 in Strasbourg, Secretary General Alain Berset stated in his opening speech: Online disinformation, polarization and manipulation undermine the trust that makes both democracy and business possible (...) Every investor, every entrepreneur, every government wants certainty – especially in these uncertain times. These threats pass through social media networks, which require rigorous fact-checking of the information disseminated and which very often affect the weakest subjects such as women¹⁵⁰, adolescents, and migrants and affect the democratic resilience¹⁵¹. Even more serious is when the false information concerns contexts of conflict and war or coexistence in fragile countries or in countries in democratic transition: the case studies highlighted in the report are to be further investigated.
101. The interferences described in the report concern disinformation and cyber-attacks. The refinement of techniques used by actors that can be traced back to the four State players analyzed, Russian Federation – People’s Republic of China – Islamic Republic of Iran – North Korea, strike from the truth of information to the functioning of critical infrastructures, from space to the depths of the seas and oceans. A landscape that requires a comprehensive and complex rethinking in terms of security strategies at national, regional and global levels. A landscape that intersects with the geopolitical upheavals taking place in every part of the world, starting with the new US Administration.
102. It has also become clear that foreign interference in modern democratic processes, and especially digital rhetoric, which is a sophisticated form of disinformation, remains one of the major threats. Another significant facet of AI and social media impact is the use of AI-generated

¹⁴⁹ Council of Europe. (21 October 2025). First Council of Europe Business and Human Rights Forum (BRAVE 2025). Council of Europe. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/portal/-/first-council-of-europe-business-and-human-rights-forum-3>

¹⁵⁰ AFP. (07 January, 2025). AI-generated deepfakes targeting women politicians around the world. Retrieved from <https://www.thehindu.com/news/international/ai-generated-deepfakes-targeting-women-politicians-around-the-world/article69071192.ece>

¹⁵¹ Hamilton, R. (08 January, 2025). Unpacking the Meta announcement: The future of the information ecosystem and implications for democracy. Retrieved from <https://www.justsecurity.org/106156/unpacking-meta-announcement-democracy/>

content, manipulation of social media, and advertisements that remain instrumental in changing people's minds, interfering with elections, and instilling polarized political views.

103. The final consideration of the report concerns the future of democracy in the current international situation crossed by the new wave of technology. Contrasting visions confront each other: on the one hand, some major technology entrepreneurs suggest a period of containment in technological development (which does not mean halting innovation) to build the best conditions for governance of the ongoing revolution and to work on strengthening democratic resilience; on the other hand, another vision, embodied by Elon Musk and others, reflects a more aggressive approach. The intertwining of a global entrepreneur like Musk with political power in the world's largest democracy shows some of the new challenges that democracies will face in the coming years.
104. Elon Musk's approach to technology and democracy favors a substantial de-regulation, and bilateral relationships based on economic interest and immediate utility on an international level. In recent years, the European Union has worked intensively to build a complex regulatory framework. The challenge now, while respecting the competences of the Member States, is to implement these rules at national level. PAM can foster a 'Mediterranean Network for Democratic Resilience in the Age of Technological Revolution' and work with other Parliamentary Assemblies and International Organizations to place democratic resilience as a key issue in national and regional security strategies.
105. A strategic shift is emerging, particularly in the United States, with regard to AI policies, which is one to be monitored carefully: from the government-with-AI to the government-by-AI. Two new policies issued by the Office of Management and Budget will usher in this era of government-by-AI: OMB Memo M-25-21 calls for accelerating federal use of AI; OMB Memo M-25-22 directs agencies to use an "efficient" acquisition process. The policies build on the administration's Jan. 23 executive order, which centered "AI dominance" as the primary aim of President Trump's AI strategy. This is a fundamental and unprecedented transformation: in fact, it will not only redefine the way federal operations are conducted but will also be a determining factor in whether AI is a democratizing force, strengthening systemic resilience, or whether it will concentrate power away from citizen control. The future of democracy itself is at stake, and not just in the US.¹⁵²

¹⁵² Frazier, K. (10 April, 2025). New White House AI policies introduce government by AI. Retrieved from <https://www.lawfaremedia.org/article/new-white-house-ai-policies-introduce-government-by-ai>

106. Along the lines of what Elon Musk has been doing since 2022¹⁵³, the social media company Meta radically changed its policy on online content moderation. Analyst David Wells wrote that the most significant consequences of Musk's actions so far have been a reduction in X's user base and revenue, rather than meaningful pushback from governments and regulators.¹⁵⁴ Meta's announcement will bring a further reduction of the already low standard in terms of content moderation: the company has more than 3 billion users around the world (Facebook, Instagram, Threads and WhatsApp). The move from fact-checking to community notes is particularly worrying, but even more so is the fact that it will affect the most vulnerable such as women, LGBTQ+ communities, and immigrants. The current trend poses several risks to lawmakers: (i) increased polarization and hate speech (with the risk of the growth of phenomena such as political violence, anti-Semitism, Islamophobia); (ii) increased online space for terrorists and extremists; (iii) negative drift in terms of resilience for human communities and democratic systems as such. Meta's decision, besides representing a decisive and dangerous change of pace, raises questions about the future of online public discourse: other organizations will follow suit, not limiting themselves to remove or mitigate fact-checking in terms of content moderation but weakening governance norms and ethical principles.

107. In an interview published on the website The Record (4 March 2025), Anne-Sophie Dhiver, the deputy head of the French government agency Viginum, emphasizes how the real problem of platform X is the potential manipulation of the algorithm to amplify or reduce the visibility of some content, which would be contrary to the European Union's Digital Services Act (DSA), as long as the platforms are not mitigating the systematic risks that could arise from the use of their services.¹⁵⁵

Next Steps

108. The report is conceived as an ongoing research project. The Permanent Parliamentary Observatory on AI and Emerging Technologies, established at PAM, will regularly produce specific Policy Briefs. Every three months, in the spirit of the research project, the Observatory will publish an update of the contents of the first report.

109. The following will also be analyzed, among other things: with regard to cyber-attacks, the perception of threats, the relative social cost and the ability of democracies to adapt; in the case

¹⁵³ Wells, D. (05 December, 2022). Why outsourcing counter-terrorism online won't work in future. Retrieved from <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/the-interpretor/why-outsourcing-counter-terrorism-online-won-t-work-future>

¹⁵⁴ Wells, D. (16 January, 2025). A Big Tech race to the bottom is bad news for everyone. Retrieved from <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/the-interpretor/big-tech-race-bottom-bad-news-everyone>

¹⁵⁵ Martin, A. (4 March, 2025). Focus on Musk's algorithms, not his words, says France's disinformation agency. The Record from Recorded Future News. Retrieved from <https://therecord.media/focus-on-musk-algorithms-not-words-france-disinfo-agency-interview>

studies identified, the scale of the threats, the depth of penetration, the evolution over time, the coordination of actors, the importance of information gaps; with regard to disinformation, case studies of interventions that have worked in terms of successful prebunking strategies, counter-narratives, coordinated platform takedowns. A strategic point of interest, fundamental to further research on disinformation, is that of monetization/demonetization.¹⁵⁶

110. It is essential for parliamentarians and civil servants, in order to provide them with analytical tools to identify concrete, proportionate and verifiable solutions, to carry out an analytical review of legislative measures that distinguishes between different areas of intervention (electoral integrity, media literacy, platform responsibility), symptomatic responses (content bans) and systemic investments (promotion of public trust, creation of civic verification infrastructures). The analysis of social platform governance is of great importance. Furthermore, recognizing the underlying uncertainty that characterizes the phenomena described in the report, the extensive scientific literature studying the real impact of disinformation phenomena and the resulting social behaviors will be explored in depth.

¹⁵⁶ Bleyer-Simon, K. (26 March 2024). (De)monetisation of disinformation: Can the actions of large online platforms be measured? Centre for Media Pluralism and Media Freedom. <https://cmpf.eui.eu/demonetisation-of-disinformation/>